

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms

Deliverable 3.1

WP3. Livestock farm energy flows assessment, smart control and simulation

Project title

RES4LIVE - Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption

Grant agreement: 101000785

From October 2020 to September 2024

Prepared by: CERTH

30/09/2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.101000785 **Disclaimer:** The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Deliverable no.	Deliverable 3.1 Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms
Responsible Partner	CERTH
WP no. and title	3. Livestock farm energy flows assessment, smart control and simulation
Task no. and title	3.1. On-farm energy demand and available renewable energy potential
Version	1
Version Date	30/09/2021

Dissemination level	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU = Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Approvals/ Document history

	Company/Institution
Author/s	CERTH
Task Leader	CERTH
WP Leader	CERTH

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101000785”. The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

ABBREVIATIONS

ATES: Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage

BTES: Borehole Thermal Energy Storage

COP: Coefficient of Performance

EEM: Energy Efficiency Measures

EAHE: Earth to Air Heat Exchangers

GSHP: Ground Source Heat Pump

HP: Heat Pump

HVAC: Heating Ventilation Air Conditioning

LCA: Life-Cycle Assessment

LPG: Liquefied Petroleum Gas

ORC: Organic Rankine Cycle

PV: Photovoltaics

PVT: Photovoltaic thermal

RES: Renewable Energy Sources

VAWT: Vertical Axis Wind Turbine

WHR: Waste Heat Sources

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

AUA - AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

UNIBO – UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ATB - LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

EV ILVO - RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURE, FISHERIES AND FOOD

UGENT - GHENT UNIVERSITY

CERTH - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY-HELLAS

AU - AARHUS UNIVERSITY

LVAT - LEHR- UND VERSUCHSANSTALT FÜR TIERZUCHT UND TIERHALTUNG GROß KREUTZ E.V.

PSYCTOTHERM - G. LIGEROS & SIA OE

PLEGMA LABS- PLEGMA LABS TECHNOLOGIKES LYSEIS ANONYMOS ETAIRIA

CRMT SAS - CENTRE DE RECHERCHES EN MACHINES THERMIQUES

TERRA - TERRA ENERGY

MG SUSTAINABLE - MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB

CETRI - CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH & INNOVATION LTD

GOLINELLI - GOLINELLI GIULIO

EAAP - FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA PER LA ZOOTECNICA

EUREC - EUREC EESV

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The overall objective of this Deliverable is to examine and quantify energy efficiency measures in typical livestock farms, point out the potential penetration of renewable energy sources as a function of energy demand/consumption and obtain a representative picture of the current energy status of the four pilot farms; towards the ultimate goal of RES4LIVE project for zero-fossil fuel consumption in livestock farming.

Initially the existing situation in typical livestock farms in EU is assessed through a comprehensive literature review. The limited available data demonstrates that the main energy consumption of livestock facilities is indirect and occurs from the production of the animal feed. On the other hand, direct on-farm energy demands constitute about ¼ of the total energy consumption and vary according to the farm type, location and its infrastructure; some basic trends are nevertheless identified. Energy audits in pig farms indicate that 44% of the direct energy consumption is associated with transportation, 31% with feeding, 12% with ventilation 3% with watering, 3% with waste removal 2% with lighting and 5% with other uses. Regarding specific energy carriers, a study shows that 48% is diesel fuel associated with vehicles and heating, 23% is liquefied petroleum gas mainly associated with heating and 29% is electricity associated with lighting, ventilation, feeding, watering and other. Studies regarding energy use in cows for milk production indicate that diesel fuel use accounts for 9% of the total demand and is associated mainly with manure handling; while electrical energy accounts for around 17% and is attributed to milk cooling, milk harvesting, water heating and water pumping, feeding, lighting and ventilation. The rest 74% of the total energy is connected to the production of the feed. As for chicken broilers, studies show that heating is the largest on-farm energy consuming activity accounting for around 92% of the total energy consumption, followed by ventilation and lighting. In warmer climates, the main energy consumption of broilers' facilities is still associated with heating but percentages vary a lot compared to colder climates. A study in Cyprus indicated that 40% of the on-farm energy demand is associated with heating, 28% with ventilation, 24% with transportation, 5% with lighting, 2% with feeding and 1% with watering. The same study concluded that enclosed chicken houses demand 30 to 40% less energy compared to open houses. Regarding specific energy carriers for broilers' houses, [enclosed / (open)] the study shows that 20% (35%) is electricity, 44% (17%) is liquefied petroleum gas, 11% (29%) is biomass and 25% (19%) is diesel fuel. However, as data is mainly scattered and individual, further research is needed to gain a better overview of the total energy consumption/concentration in EU livestock farming.

Based on the above, livestock sector is a significant energy consumer of different energy carriers and has a considerable effect in natural resources. Therefore, it should be managed as an integrated system, given the increasing scarcity of land, soil, water and biodiversity. Renewable energy sources and energy efficiency measures and technologies in combination with energy conservation practices provide a unique opportunity for livestock farms to reduce energy consumption and produce their own clean energy to become partially or totally self-sufficient. Solar energy, wind energy, hydropower, biomass, heat pumps and geothermal energy can be utilized to produce electricity and fuels in order to adequately cover partly or exclusively the on-farm energy demands, always in the scope of adequately satisfying the animals' comfort prerequisites. Some factors that influence the renewable energy sources penetration and efficiency in livestock farming are, indicatively (i) the location of the farm, (ii) the local environment, (iii) the buildings' characteristics, (iv) the domestic needs and energy consumption profile of each farm, and (v) the planning policies for these technologies in rural areas. Selecting the most appropriate renewable energy technology for a specific farm should be thoroughly studied taking into account all the aforementioned factors in combination with the farm type and the needs that arise from it.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Solar energy, bioenergy, heat pumps, wind energy and organic Rankine cycle applications hold great potential to be applied to all types of farms, covering an extremely wide range of energy needs. Moreover, geothermal energy units also have potential in the livestock sector since they have the ability to store the excess energy produced and supply it when needed. More specifically, solar energy can be utilized in all types of farms, being able to put up for both electricity and heating needs, having as major performance factors the solar radiation and the local air temperature of a location. Bioenergy poses some great advantages, as its flexibility allows for integration into a wide spectrum of existing energy systems, especially in areas with large grassland and arable crops which in terms produce residual biomass allocated either as animal feed or as fuel for biomass boilers; also as a waste management solution as organic waste and especially wood-based materials provide valuable feedstock. Some factors that restrict bioenergy wider outspread are land use change, food security, biodiversity, energy efficiency and cost. Heat pumps' potential is focused towards applications that allow their coupling with photovoltaic-thermal hybrid solar collectors or geothermal units, especially in poultry and pig farms. In general, their viability increases where a cooling demand is present, as their capital cost is spread over heating and cooling savings. Geothermal energy systems can be utilized for livestock applications where there is a need for heating and/or cooling, regardless of the farm type; however, they are preferable in dairy and pig farms since they can restore variable heating and cooling needs. Their application must be investigated per climate zone, as the available average temperature of the subsurface fluctuates greatly from northern to southern Europe. Wind energy constitutes one of the most promising renewable energy sources, especially in poultry and pig farms, since they have high electrical energy demand mainly for ventilation and lighting. Apart from that, their implementation in livestock farming is well adaptable to all farm types, since they can be installed stand-alone, away from the farm's buildings. The main factors that need to be investigated prior to their installation are the wind and icing conditions of the area and the noise generated during their operation as it could oppose the animals' comfort. Organic Rankine cycle engines are frequently used in small scale applications in alignment with steam engines, gasification systems with the possibility of hot air and Sterling engines. These systems can be fitted in all types of farms providing both power and heat from the same produced by-products (manure, sludge, solid biomass). Nevertheless, most promising renewable energy sources technologies and energy efficiency measures for specific farm types/locations cannot be easily/absolutely derived as this task constitutes a demanding procedure that combines various factors.

Based on the analysis of energy consumption allocation and potential use of renewable energy sources in livestock facilities, a series of audits were carried out within RES4LIVE to extract a reliable estimation of the current energy demand. This information will be later verified according to real data which will be derived from the instrumentation arrangements that will be installed in the pilot farms, as foreseen in Task 3.3. This data will among else be utilized to quantify precisely the effect of the RES4LIVE planned interventions. The energy consumption allocation for each farm type (swine, cattle and poultry) is presented in 4 levels of detail; (a) per energy type (e.g. heat, electricity, etc.), (b) per specific building (e.g. gestation barn, nursery barn, etc.), (c) per specific device/device type (e.g. lights, fans, etc.) and (d) in working time (hours per month). Feed and milk data were also recorded where available, but it was not deemed appropriate to be displayed in this report as they are not directly connected to energy consumers. The energy consumption varies both in energy type and usage. For example, the swine pilot farm in Belgium utilizes annually 115,000 kWh of electrical energy for multiple purposes (including a fraction for heating) and about 220,000 kWh of energy from natural gas solely for heating. The dairy pilot farm in Germany consumes annually about 201,000 kWh of electrical energy for milk production only. Despite its small size, poultry farm in Greece corresponds to the literature results, with ventilation fans being the highest energy consumers. The simulations for the swine farm in Italy adequately depicted the temperature

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

distribution and the energy flows with the given data; however, real energy consumption measurements will provide the most accurate picture for the two specific buildings of interest. In all farms, the trends of the energy consumption allocation throughout the year are as expected. Manure management, lighting and feeding trends are mostly stable; while heating/cooling demands are alternating during the colder/warmer months, respectively.

Within RES4LIVE, different interventions are planned according to the needs and renewable energy sources' availability of each separate farm. These interventions will be combined with energy efficiency measures such as insulation envelopes and equipment upgrading. Additionally, smart energy control will be implemented in order to cost-effectively manage the energy flows (e.g. minimize energy demand from fossil fuel consumption), while satisfying the animals' thermal comfort needs for welfare and high productivity.

As a future step, Deliverable 3.5 will be produced, containing the energy consumption and distribution of the 4 pilot farms, ideally for a full year period, using data derived from the sensors installed in the context of Task 3.3.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 INTRODUCTION	13
1.1 Overall and specific objectives	13
2 LITERATURE REVIEW ABOUT ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN TYPICAL LIVESTOCK FARMS.....	14
2.1 Identification of energy consumption in typical livestock farms	14
2.1.1 Pigs	14
2.1.2 Bovine animals	16
2.1.2.1 Beef.....	16
2.1.2.2 Cows for milk production	17
2.1.3 Poultry	18
2.1.3.1 Chicken Broilers.....	18
2.1.3.2 Chicken Egg Production.....	20
2.2 Synopsis	21
3 POTENTIAL FOR RES TECHNOLOGIES AND EFFICIENCY MEASURES IN LIVESTOCK FARMS.....	22
3.1 RES penetration into the energy requirements of livestock farms	23
3.1.1 Solar energy.....	23
3.1.2 Wind Energy	23
3.1.3 Hydro Power.....	24
3.1.4 Geothermal Energy	24
3.1.5 Biomass	25
3.1.6 Heat pumps	25
3.2 Factors that influence RES involvement and efficiency	25
3.3 Potential Applications	26
4 MOST PROMISING RES TECHNOLOGIES AND EFFICIENCY MEASURES FOR LIVESTOCK FARMS	28
4.1 Solar Energy Applications	29
4.2 Bioenergy Applications.....	30
4.3 Applications of Heat Pumps	31
4.4 Geothermal Energy Applications.....	32
4.5 Wind Energy Applications	32
4.6 ORC Applications	33
5 EXISTING SITUATION OF PILOT LIVESTOCK FARMS – ENERGY AUDITS	35
5.1 Energy Audits as an Energy Efficiency tool.....	35
5.2 Methodology of data collection	37

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

5.3 Existing situation of pilot farms.....	38
5.3.1 Pilot farm in Belgium (swine)	38
5.3.2 Pilot farm in Italy (swine)	40
5.3.3 Pilot farm in Germany (dairy).....	45
5.3.4 Pilot farm in Greece (poultry).....	48
5.4 Renewable Energy Potential and most promising RES in Local Farm Areas	52
5.5 Future work	53
6 CONCLUSIONS	54
7 REFERENCES	56

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Energy inputs for pig production slaughter weight MJ/kg [2]–[4].	15
Table 2. Total energy inputs for pork production EU-27 (PJ).	15
Table 3. Direct energy inputs in pig production systems according to activity [5].	15
Table 4. Total energy inputs for beef production EU-27 (PJ).	16
Table 5. Energy inputs cow milk MJ ECM [2], [12]–[14].	17
Table 6. Total energy inputs for cow milk production EU-27.	17
Table 7. Electrical energy breakdown dairy farms EU [15].	18
Table 8. Energy inputs chicken broilers carcass weight MJ/kg [2], [17].	19
Table 9. Energy inputs for poultry production EU-27 (PJ).	19
Table 10. Heating, ventilation and lighting energy consumption broiler farms in MJ/kgmeat [18].	19
Table 11. Thermal and electrical energy consumption broiler farms in MJ/kgmeat [18].	19
Table 12. Energy inputs for egg producing systems MJ/kg [19].	20

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Breakdown of pork production in EU-28.....	14
Figure 2. Breakdown of poultry production in EU-28 (2018).....	18
Figure 3. Direct energy consumption in egg production systems in Cyprus (Markou et al., 2017).	21
Figure 4. Farm scale solar, wind and biomass facilities.....	22
Figure 5. Schematic illustration of a basic PV system for a swine farm (Green et al., 2002).	27
Figure 6. (a) ILVO farm, outside view and (b) plain schematic of the two sections with the common ceiling.	38
Figure 7. ILVO farm’s electrical energy consumption allocation throughout a year (2020).	39
Figure 8. ILVO farm’s natural gas consumption allocation throughout a year (2020).	40
Figure 9. ILVO farm’s fuel oil consumption allocation throughout a year (2020).	40
Figure 10. (a) GOLINELLI farm building 12, outside view and (b) general layout plan of the farm.....	41
Figure 11. Temperature distribution (colour coded scalar field) and thermal flows (vector field) in GOLINELLI farm Building 12 for three different ambient temperatures.....	42
Figure 12. Temperature distribution (colour coded scalar field) and thermal flows (vector field) in GOLINELLI farm Building 16 for three different ambient temperatures.....	43
Figure 13. Yearly allocation of the energy requirements for temperature control in Building 12 of GOLINELLI farm.....	44
Figure 14. Yearly allocation of the energy requirements for temperature control in Building 16 of GOLINELLI farm.....	44
Figure 15. (a) LVAT farm barns 29 & 1, outside view and (b) general layout plan of the farm.	45
Figure 16. Breakdown of LVAT farm’s electrical energy demand.	46
Figure 17. Electrical energy consumption of LVAT’s farm per barn.....	47
Figure 18. LPG consumption of LVAT’s farm per barn and usage.	47
Figure 20. (a) AUA poultry farm inside view and (b) location of the farm within the AUA campus.	49
Figure 21. Yearly allocation of the electrical energy consumption of AUA’s farm per need.	49
Figure 22. Temperature distribution (colour coded scalar field) and thermal flows (vector field) in AUA farm for three different ambient temperatures.	51
Figure 23. Yearly allocation of the energy requirements for temperature control in AUA farm.	52

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overall and specific objectives

The overall objective of this report is to examine and quantify energy efficiency measures in typical livestock farms and to point out the potential penetration of RES (Renewable Energy Sources) as a function of energy demand/consumption, towards the ultimate RES4LIVE project goal of zero-fossil fuel consumption in livestock farms.

Obtaining a representative picture of the current situation/energy demand in the 4 pilot farms, and specifically in the buildings of interest at farm level, will additionally assist in identifying/quantifying the outcome of the planned interventions of the project, after these have been implemented.

This Deliverable's specific objectives can be summarized as follows:

- (a) Assessment of the existing situation in typical livestock farms in the EU based on an up to date literature review;
- (b) Identification of the most promising RES and Energy Efficiency Measures (EEM) and technologies for each type of livestock farm;
- (c) Assessment of the existing situation on the pilot farms by conducting comprehensive energy audits and highlighting areas of high energy consumption;
- (d) Determination of the RES potential in local farm areas based on the data acquired from the previous tasks.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

2 LITERATURE REVIEW ABOUT ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN TYPICAL LIVESTOCK FARMS

2.1 Identification of energy consumption in typical livestock farms

The following section is dedicated to the identification of the energy consumption in the EU livestock sector. According to data from Eurostat for the year 2018¹ (Eurostat, 2020), the main livestock populations in the EU consisted of 148 million pigs, 87 million bovine animals and 350 million egg laying hens. The rearing of livestock for animal products is widespread with more than half, 5.7 million, of the agricultural holdings in the EU keeping livestock. Based on the above, it is evident that there is an urgent need for EU to turn to more environmentally friendly and, at the same time, efficient practices in order to minimize the overall energy consumption in the livestock sector. The livestock farm types that will be discussed in this section concern pigs, bovine animals and poultry.

2.1.1 Pigs

Europe's meat production is heavily based on pork meat, and this is evident from the fact that in 2018 an overall all time high was reached with around 23.8 million tonnes of pig meat being produced, which accounts for almost half of the EU's meat production for that year. According to Eurostat the two main producing Member States are Germany (22.4%) and Spain (19%) (Figure 1) (Eurostat, 2020).

Figure 1. Breakdown of pork production in EU-28.

According to our research and in collaboration with AgroFossilFree Horizon 2020 Project we can conclude that for each kg of slaughter weight pork produced, a total of 17.91 MJ of energy inputs are required. In Table 1 the energy inputs for pig production are presented. Even though there is some variation between the studies (Table 2), it is evident that feed production is the largest energy

¹ Data presented is from 2018 and not more recent, because little to no studies were published after this year which analyse in detail the energy consumption in the livestock sector.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

consumer, with almost 72% of the total energy consumption whereas the remaining 28% is about direct on-farm energy use.

Table 1. Energy inputs for pig production slaughter weight MJ/kg (Basset-Mens and Van Der Werf, 2005; Nguyen, Hermansen and Mogensen, 2010b; Gołaszewski et al., 2012).

Source	Country	Feed	Maintenance	Diesel Use	Other	Total
de Visser et al. 2012	Portugal	13.4			5.9	19.3
de Visser et al. 2012	Poland	13.9		1.5	2.4	17.8
de Visser et al. 2012	Netherlands	11.90			2.60	14.50
de Visser et al. 2012	Germany	11.80		0.20	2.90	14.90
de Visser et al. 2012	Finland	11.60	1.60		9.50	22.70
Basset-Mens & van der Werf, 2005	France	11.77		4.13		15.90
Nguyen et al., 2010	Nguyen EU	16.41		3.84		20.25
	EU Average	12.97		4.94		17.91
	EU Average (%)	72%		28%		100%

Table 2. Total energy inputs for pork production EU-27 (PJ).

Total pork production EU-27 (m tonnes)	Feed	Direct energy use	Total
23.8	199.58	74.17	273.74

Another factor which affects the energy consumption in pig farming and, more specifically, the breakdown between the direct energy inputs, is the geographical location of the farms. In spite of that, the majority of direct energy use is associated with manure management, housing and feeding systems in the form of electricity and fuels. For example, according to Nguyen et al.'s (Nguyen, Hermansen and Mogensen, 2012) overview of on-farm energy use in Northern Europe, the findings suggest that 3.84 MJ of direct energy is required per kg of slaughter weight pig meat². The breakdown of the total energy consumption is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Direct energy inputs in pig production systems according to activity (Nguyen, Hermansen and Mogensen, 2012).

Activity	Energy input MJ	% of direct energy inputs
Diesel use	0.87	22%
Housing – Electricity	1.95	50%
Housing heat –oil	0.65	17%
Manure pumping and stirring – Electricity	0.4	10%

Furthermore, this study also finds that the use of manure for energy production, fertilization and reducing feed use are the most significant factors in reducing the use of fossil energy use in pig systems (Nguyen, Hermansen and Mogensen, 2012).

On the other hand, Markou et al. (Markou et al., 2017) conducted energy audits on two pig farms in Cyprus. According to their findings on direct energy inputs, 44% of energy consumption is associated with transportation, 31% with feeding, 12% with ventilation, 3% with watering, 3% with waste removal, 2% with lighting and 5% with other uses. Furthermore, regarding specific energy carriers,

² The energy consumption of the slaughterhouse is not included as well as the energy consumed for the pork processing. The reviewed system's boundary ends right before the entry to the slaughterhouse.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

this study finds that 29% is electricity associated with lighting, ventilation, feeding, watering, and other uses, 23% is LPG (Liquefied Petroleum Gas) mainly associated with heating and 48% is diesel associated with vehicle use and heating.

Other studies conducted in Austria and Germany (Winkler *et al.*, 2016), have found that for heating, ventilation, lighting and manure management purposes, 1.26 MJ of electrical energy and 0.684 MJ of thermal energy are required. In addition to these, field manipulation and on-farm transportation create a demand for 4.356 MJ of mechanical energy per kg of pork produced,

2.1.2 Bovine animals

Bovine meat consists of beef derived from certain cattle breeds as well as veal. The EU production of bovine meat during 2018 was 7.9 million tonnes. According to Eurostat, the main producing countries for that year were France and Germany for beef and The Netherlands and Spain for veal (Eurostat, 2020).

2.1.2.1 Beef

Multiple studies suggest that the production of beef has the highest environmental production load per kg of meat produced when compared to the main livestock systems (McAuliffe *et al.*, 2018). Based on these findings, on average 59.2 MJ/kg of beef is required for a suckler cow-calf and 43.73 MJ/kg for a dairy bull. Furthermore, considering that almost 60% of beef production in EU comes from dairy bulls and the remaining 40% comes from suckler cows-calves, the total energy inputs for beef production systems were estimated at 226.76 PJ for the EU as a whole. The breakdown of this shows that 36% of the total energy inputs are used for feed and fertilizers (Table 4). It should be mentioned that there is a significant difference in the energy input in feed depending on whether a cow is fed on grass-pasture or concentrate-confinement, as pasture requires significantly lower energy inputs for cultivation and fertilization operations (Frorip *et al.*, 2012). European cows are generally grown on a combination of home-grown grass and cereals as well as imported soy meal and minerals (Nguyen, Hermansen and Mogensen, 2010a).

Table 4. Total energy inputs for beef production EU-27 (PJ).

Production System	Total beef production EU-27	Feed	Fertilizers	Fuel	Other	Total
EU Suckler cow-calf	3.16	20.82	18.51	40.87	27.37	107.57
EU Dairy bulls	4.74	23.07	20.51	45.29	30.33	119.20
EU Total	7.90	43.89	39.01	86.15	57.71	226.76
EU Average %		19%	17%	38%	25%	100%

Regarding the breakdown of direct energy use in Nguyen *et al.*'s study (Nguyen, Hermansen and Mogensen, 2010a), it is highlighted that 71% of direct energy use comes in the form of on-farm diesel use (due to manure management and field operations) whereas 17% is on-farm electricity usage in stables and housing accounts. The remaining 11% is electricity used in crop processing. From the above we can conclude that most of the energy consumption in beef production systems is associated with on-farm activities. Another highlight of the aforementioned study is that direct energy usage the purpose of fattening is the largest consumer, accounting for 50-58% of the total energy consumption in beef production systems (Nguyen, Hermansen and Mogensen, 2010a).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

2.1.2.2 Cows for milk production

Besides of the energy consumed for beef production, another energy consuming process is the production of cow milk. According to Eurostat (Eurostat, no date), around 158 million tons of cow milk are produced annually. Among the main producing EU countries are Germany (20.8%), France (15.8%), The Netherlands (8.9%) and Poland (7.7%). Based on the data available from LCAs (Life-cycle assessment) and studies, it can be concluded that, on average, each kg of milk produced requires 3.42 MJ of energy inputs. From the data shown on [Table 5](#) & [Table 6](#), it is evident that the energy demand for feed is the main energy input, accounting for around 74% of the total energy. By combining all the available data, we get an estimation of the required energy for the entire production of cow milk in EU, which is 540 PJ. Diesel fuel use (mainly manure handling) accounts for around 9% and other (mainly electrical energy in milking systems, feeding, lighting and ventilation) accounts for around 17%.

Table 5. Energy inputs cow milk MJ ECM (Cederberg and Stadig, 2003; Gołaszewski et al., 2012; Guerci et al., 2013; Upton, 2014).

Source	Country	Feed	Diesel Use	Other (mainly electricity)	Total
de Visser et al. 2012	Portugal	2.12	0.30	0.80	3.22
de Visser et al. 2012	Poland	3.90	0.60	0.42	5.05
de Visser et al. 2012	Netherlands	3.30	0.60	0.70	4.60
de Visser et al. 2012	Germany	1.70	0.15	0.60	2.71
de Visser et al. 2012	Finland	2.90	0.00	0.70	3.86
Upton, 2014	Ireland	1.86	0.19	0.35	2.40
Cederberg and Flysjö, 2003	Sweden	1.76		0.95	2.70
Thomassen et al., 2009	NL	4.40		0.87	5.3 FPCM
Guerci et al., 2013	Denmark average	2.02		1.76	3.78
Guerci et al., 2013	Germany average	1.34		0.97	2.32
Guerci et al., 2013	Italy average	2.47		1.08	3.54
	EU Average	2.52	0.31	0.59	3.42
	EU Average (%)	74%	9%	17%	100%

Table 6. Total energy inputs for cow milk production EU-27.

Total cow milk production EU-27 (m tonnes)	Feed	Diesel Use	Other (mainly electricity)	Total
158.52	400.04	48.61	94.27	542.92

Regarding the direct energy usage, it is estimated that on-farm electrical consumption is associate with milk cooling (36%), milk harvesting (32%), water heating (23%) and water pumping (9%) ([Table 7](#)). It should be mentioned that, between the different studies, there is a range of factors which affect the final results, the most important being the production system and the type of milking system (Shine et al., 2020).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Table 7. Electrical energy breakdown dairy farms EU (Shine et al., 2020).

Source	Country	Milk cooling	Milk harvesting	Water heating	Water pumping
Murgia et al. 2013	Italy	38%	31%	13%	18%
Todde et al. 2018	Italy	29%	35%	23%	14%
Rajaniemi et al. 2017	Finland	42%	23%	32%	3%
Shine et al. 2018	Ireland	41%	25%	28%	6%
Shortall et al. 2018	Ireland	29%	53%	11%	7%
Upton et al. 2013	Ireland	39%	25%	29%	6%
	EU average %	36%	32%	23%	9%

2.1.3 Poultry

The second largest category of meat production in EU is poultry. According to Eurostat, an unprecedented all-time high in poultry production was reached in 2018 with almost 15.2 million tonnes produced. The main poultry meat producers among the EU countries are presented in the following graph (Figure 2), with Poland being the biggest producer at 2.5 million tonnes, followed by the United Kingdom at 2 million tonnes (Eurostat, 2020). Furthermore, it should be mentioned that during the same period there were almost 350 million egg laying hens in the EU that produced around 6.7 million tonnes of eggs (Commission, 2017).

Figure 2. Breakdown of poultry production in EU-28 (2018).

2.1.3.1 Chicken Broilers

According to our research, for each kg of meat produced in broilers, 12.96 MJ of energy is required, of which 74% is related to feed production and distribution and 26% to on-farm energy demand (Table 8 & Table 9).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Table 8. Energy inputs chicken broilers carcass weight MJ/kg (Gołaszewski *et al.*, 2012; Prudêncio da Silva *et al.*, 2014).

Source	Country	Feed	Maintenance	Diesel Use	Other	Total
de Visser <i>et al.</i> 2012	Portugal	8.3		0.2		8.5
de Visser <i>et al.</i> 2012 ³	Portugal	12.1			0.5	12.6
de Visser <i>et al.</i> 2012	Poland	8.20		2.90	3.70	14.80
de Visser <i>et al.</i> 2012	Netherlands	10.10	1.00		2.80	13.90
de Visser <i>et al.</i> 2012	Germany	6.50	0.30	2.90		9.70
de Visser <i>et al.</i> 2012	Finland	7.30	0.30		4.60	12.20
Silva <i>et al.</i> , 2014	France	14.82		4.28		19.10
	EU Average	9.62		3.35		12.97
	EU Average (%)	74%		26%		100%

Table 9. Energy inputs for poultry production EU-27 (PJ).

Total poultry production EU-27	Feed	Other	Total
15.20	146.18	50.99	197.17

Constantino *et al.* (Constantino *et al.*, 2016) attempted to investigate the direct energy consumption in broiler farms by synthesizing the data available from multiple sources. The results of that study indicate that heating is by far the largest on-farm energy consuming activity, accounting for around 92% of the total energy consumption, followed by ventilation at 5% and lighting at 3% (Table 10); according to Table 11, 92% is associated with thermal energy and the remaining 8% with electrical energy. It should be noted that the data shown on these tables do not include energy inputs related to feeding and manure management. Furthermore, the same case of the geographical variation as in the pork meat production occurs for poultry as well.

Table 10. Heating, ventilation and lighting energy consumption broiler farms in MJ/kg_{meat} (Constantino *et al.*, 2016).

Source	Country	Heating	Ventilation	Lighting
Amand <i>et al.</i> 2009	France	1.37	0.11	0.07
ADEME 2010	France	1.51	0.15	0.10
Arellano 2011	Spain	5.45	0.17	0.03
Arellano 2011	Spain	2.73	0.17	0.01
Arellano 2011	Spain	1.64	0.17	0.01
Rossi <i>et al.</i> 2013	Italy	2.23	0.12	0.03
Hörndahl 2008	Sweden	1.73	0.07	0.22
	EU Average	2.38	0.14	0.07
	EU Average %	92%	5%	3%

Table 11. Thermal and electrical energy consumption broiler farms in MJ/kg_{meat} (Constantino *et al.*, 2016).

Source	Country	Thermal	Electrical
Amand <i>et al.</i> 2009	France	1.37	0.18
ADEME 2010	France	1.51	0.25
Arellano 2011	Spain	5.45	0.19
Arellano 2011	Spain	2.73	0.18
Arellano 2011	Spain	1.64	0.17
Blázquez & Del Olmo, 2008	Italy	1.40	0.01

³ Appears like same author/work presenting deviated data for the same countries. This is due to the cited author reviewing different cases for different system boundaries.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Rossi et al. 2013	Italy	2.15	0.23
Hörndahl 2008	Sweden	1.73	0.30
	EU Average	2.25	0.19
	EU Average %	92%	8%

The geographical variation is more evident in warmer climates, where even though most of the consumed energy is associated primarily with heating and then with ventilation, the percentages vary a lot compared to colder climates. For example, Markou et al. (Markou *et al.*, 2017) in their study which took place in Cyprus found that 40% of energy is associated with heating, 28% with ventilation, 24% with transportation, 5% with lights, 2% with feeding and 1% with watering. Another conclusion of that study was that closed chicken houses have 30-40% less energy consumption when compared to open houses. In closed broiler houses, most of the energy used came from fossil fuels (65%) and the remaining percentage is energy from the electrical grid (35%). On the other hand, for open broiler houses, the energy produced from fuels is 80% and the remaining 20% is electricity. The breakdown of the specific energy carriers used for open broilers is 35% electricity, 17% LPG, 29% biomass and 19% diesel, while for the closed type it is 20% electricity, 44% LPG, 11% biomass and 25% diesel (Markou *et al.*, 2017).

2.1.3.2 Chicken Egg Production

The available data on chicken egg production in EU is fragmented, therefore posing a challenge to when it comes to drawing solid conclusions. The most comprehensive approach in the aforementioned section can be attributed to Dekker et al.', even though their study is geographically limited (Dekker *et al.*, 2011). Particularly in this study, the energy consumption from four egg production systems in The Netherlands is studied. The results, which cover the main production systems in EU, show that the production of 1 kg of eggs requires 20.5-23.5 MJ of energy inputs and that in all cases at least 50% of all energy inputs are associated with feed. A more detailed breakdown of the different energy inputs is presented on [Table 12](#).

Table 12. Energy inputs for egg producing systems MJ/kg (Dekker *et al.*, 2011).

Source	Country	Feed	Hatching and Rearing	Laying hen husbandry	Transport	Total
Dekker et al., 2011	NL Battery Cage	11.2	0.9	1.9	6.6	20.6
Dekker et al., 2011	NL Barn	12.90	1.00	0.80	8.25	22.95
Dekker et al., 2011	NL Freerange	13.20	1.05	0.80	8.45	23.5
Dekker et al., 2011	NL Organic	10.30	1.50	1.10	7.65	20.55
	Average %	50%	7%	5%	37%	100%

By studying the findings of available studies, it can be concluded that the largest amount of the energy consumed in chicken egg production is for feeding systems. For instance, in Leinonen et al.'s study (Leinonen *et al.*, 2012), an LCA was conducted on the environmental impacts of chicken egg systems in the UK and the results showed that feed amounts to approximately 54-75% of the total energy use; followed by on-farm electricity usage (mainly for ventilation, automatic feeding and lighting), which accounts for approximately 16-38% of the total energy consumption. The remaining percentage is gas and oil usage (mainly for heating and incineration of dead layer birds), which accounts for 7-14% of the total primary energy (Leinonen *et al.*, 2012). In the same note, Markou et al.'s study (Markou *et al.*, 2017) concludes that feed represents around 83% of the total energy consumption. In terms of direct energy consumption, the study finds that over on third of energy used is for ventilation purposes (33%), followed by transportation (17%), lighting (15%), thermal energy (3%), waste removal (2%), packaging (14%), watering (1%) and feeding (15%). Regarding the

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

specific energy carriers, the study finds that electricity accounts for 55%, Diesel fuel for 33% and LPG for 12% (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Direct energy consumption in egg production systems in Cyprus (Markou et al., 2017).

2.2 Synopsis

The data presented in this Section clearly indicate that, in all livestock systems except for beef production systems, animal feed is the main energy input amounting to approximately 75% of all energy requirements. The production of animal feed consumes around 60% of the cereal production in the EU and requires significant high-protein imports. There is a demand in the EU market for feed to move towards locally produced solutions. If the energy intensity of animal feed was reduced, then the overall energy consumption would also be reduced. For the record, in that note, EIP-AGRI identified 5 new feed options for pig and poultry farming that would help to reduce the environmental footprint of animal feed. These options include bakery products, green biomass (grass/clover), insects, micro-algae and single cell protein (EIP-AGRI, 2020).

Farm electricity usage, which currently comes mainly from fossil fuel sources, is also significant but varies considerably depending on the production system. Electricity is mainly used for lighting, feeding and milking systems whereas fossil fuels are more often used for manure management and heating. In order to reduce the amount of fossil energy used, measures should be taken in order to encourage the usage of renewable energy sources. However, further research is required to fully understand the problem and gain a more comprehensive overview of the total energy consumption and concentration, as the data is either fragmented or lacking (i.e., small farms).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

3 POTENTIAL FOR RES TECHNOLOGIES AND EFFICIENCY MEASURES IN LIVESTOCK FARMS

According to the data discussed in the previous chapter, electricity and fossil fuels constitute the main sources of energy in livestock farms, fully covering -in most cases- demand. The energy consumption to maintain proper conditions within a livestock structure (including the control of temperature, humidity, lighting, ventilation, and the chemical environment) is of great interest since farm animals are positively affected if these conditions remain at certain desirable, or at least acceptable, levels. Additionally, it has been proven that farm animals grown in conditions beyond their thermo-neutral zone demonstrate reduced productivity and/or are easily affected by diseases (Seedorf *et al.*, 1998; Firfiris, Martzopoulou and Kotsopoulos, 2019).

However, when it comes to buildings' heating, the estimation of the total energy consumption in most cases is a demanding task, as a wide range of factors is involved. The most significant among these factors are: (a) the difference between the desirable indoor and the outdoor climate conditions, (b) the insulation of the buildings and (c) the surface area exposed to ambient conditions (walls, floor, roof). Theoretically, it is possible to estimate the energy consumption for given conditions using approximations. Nevertheless, in order to have a more accurate estimation, advanced mathematical models are required that will also take into account the effect of the location of the farm (e.g. geographical position and orientation), the influence of the wind speed and direction, as well as the effect of neighboring buildings and vegetation on the building climate of the building. For example, in the case of fattening pig production especially in north Europe, additional heating is required only for drying the barn and keeping it warm before the arrival of the pigs. In piglet production (all types of pens except deep litter), this additional heating is required for some weeks during farrowing and particularly during weaning when the sow has been moved, to ensure a well heated environment for the piglets (Horndahl, 2008).

In general, the optimum growth of farm animals is achieved between a specific range of temperatures and humidity, based on which the buildings' thermal/cooling needs are calculated. The local climate and the structural characteristics of the building can also play a major role in the aforementioned calculations. The omission of these parameters can lead to a number of discrepancies in the final results. RES and EEM and technologies integration in livestock farming has to be studied in the scope of adequately satisfying the animals' comfort prerequisites.

Figure 4. Farm scale solar, wind and biomass facilities.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

3.1 RES penetration into the energy requirements of livestock farms

Considering the effect that the livestock sector has in numerous natural resources and given the increasing scarcity of land, soil, water and biodiversity, it should be commonly accepted that this sector must be carefully managed as an integrated system. The increasing usage of RES and EEM and technologies throughout the world -especially in colder climate countries (Kothari, Tyagi and Pathak, 2010; Lee *et al.*, 2010)- in combination with energy conservation practices, provide a unique opportunity to the farmers to reduce their farms' external inputs by producing their own energy and becoming more self-sufficient. With an initial investment, energy can be harvested for free out of variable renewable energy sources such as the sun, wind and water. These sources in addition with the biomass, the heat pumps and the geothermal energy can produce electricity and fuel in order to adequately cover partly, or exclusively, -depending on the size- the on-farm energy demand.

3.1.1 Solar energy

Solar energy can be broadly categorized into: (a) solar photovoltaic (PV) technologies and (b) solar thermal technologies. In small scale, solar energy has been widely used to cover multiple small/medium-scale applications both on municipal and agricultural level. At community level the sun's energy can be used for passive heating (e.g., in greenhouses; a cost-effective option for small growers interested in extending their growing season), solar thermal heating for hot water systems (in a similar fashion to passive solar by collecting and storing heat) and in alignment with Photovoltaics (PV) it can be used to convert the solar energy to electricity. Moreover, with the proliferation of solar energy generation the interest in on-farm solar generation has grown.

Generally, farms use a significant amount of energy, including diesel fuel for tractors and trucks, heating oil and/or propane for buildings, water heaters, and electricity for refrigeration, lighting, and ventilation. A properly designed solar project can deliver electricity and/or income for farms seeking to reduce their expenses, while in parallel they can protect primary agricultural soils promoting solar and active agricultural use on the same land (Rota *et al.*, 2012; *Guide to Farming Friendly Solar*, 2017; Lämmle, Herrando and Ryan, 2020).

3.1.2 Wind Energy

Wind energy is an abundant energy resource that offers a unique opportunity to deliver stable financial rewards with little or no effort on the part of landowners. Depending on location, a farm might find that wind generation is possible. Generally, wind farms provide an alternative income stream for farmers since they can produce electricity covering a large portion of the average power needs of a farm, with a minimum footprint. Wind energy can be considered as one of the safest and most environmentally-friendly sources of electricity available today due to the fact that it emits no greenhouse gases or pollutants and does not use fresh water – which results in a healthier, cleaner environment for crops, livestock and farmers, alike. Farm-scale turbines come in a certain range of sizes, depending on the technology they make use of and their output power. However, for the implementation in livestock farms, installing wind turbines stand-alone in open areas away from the buildings is preferred to achieve maximum energy harness. Furthermore, wind energy can be proposed for pumping water in remote locations as well as for recovering energy from livestock buildings' ventilation systems (Canadian Wind Energy Association, 2018).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

3.1.3 Hydro Power

Hydro power is a clean and emission free renewable energy technology and is widely promoted as an environment friendly option. It can be used by a small community of people, especially if there is a small running body of water nearby and just like in solar and wind energy, hydro power projects can be classified into large scale or small scale. Small scale hydropower generation, also referred to as micro-hydro, is a way of harnessing the energy of flowing water and putting that energy to mechanical or electrical use. Typical small-hydro systems are designed to generate 2 MW of energy or less and have the advantage of multiple uses: energy generation, irrigation, and water supply. Mechanical hydropower systems utilize the pressure of an irrigation system to spin the turbines and drive a hydraulic pump that is responsible for advancing the center pivot around the field. In this instance, no electricity is generated or required to move the center pivot. Another type of hydropower system, the hydroelectric type, harnesses the energy of water to spin a turbine or waterwheel and generate electrical energy through a generator coupled to the turbine shaft. Hydroelectric systems can be costly but may offer the irrigator a way of generating electricity that reduces utility bills. The advantages of installing a hydroelectric system on a farm depend greatly on a good source of water with a constant flow. If these conditions exist and the farm's power needs are well documented, the farmer may opt for one of several mechanisms: waterwheels, impulse turbines, or reaction turbines. While waterwheels are less efficient than turbines and most suitable for powering grinders, they are relatively simple to use and can handle a wide range in water flow and debris. Turbines require a more controlled and constant rate of flow as well as a greater head or elevation difference from the source of the water to the turbine blades. In general, the larger the hydroelectric system, the cheaper the produced energy. Although small hydropower generation may be easier to implement than before, hydroelectric facilities are still subject to regulation and therefore rendering this energy source untapped (KRISTOFERSON and BOKALDERS, 1986; Osborn, Weiner and Anderson, 2017).

3.1.4 Geothermal Energy

Geothermal energy is the natural heat from the earth's interior stored in rocks and water within the earth's crust. The main source of this energy is the constant flow of heat from the earth's interior towards the surface. This heat creates the molten rock, or magma, beneath the surface crust. This source of energy can be accessed through drilling wells to tap concentrations of steam at high pressures and at depths shallow enough to be economically justifiable. The steam is then led by pipes to drive electricity-generating turbines. Geothermal power exploitation has numerous advantages over other energy sources. Like wind energy, geothermal power has near zero emissions (true for modern closed cycle systems that re-inject water back to the earth's crust), and the little space required for geothermal power development compared to other energy sources such as coal fired plants (Herbert *et al.*, 2014).

Geothermal technologies can be applied in different energy concepts in the livestock sector. Farm buildings can use geothermal heat pumps to exchange air temperature and ground temperature year-round, keeping buildings cool in summer and warm in winter. While geothermal systems are more expensive to purchase and install than a typical fossil fuel burning furnace, the payback time is 5 to 10 years given the free fuel (Mariita, 2002; Alberti *et al.*, 2018).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

3.1.5 Biomass

In general, biomass is a renewable energy source, the term referring to any material that has been created as a consequence of a human or animal activity, but has not generated any economic value in the context, and its energy use can turn a residue into a by-product. The agricultural biomass holds the lion's share, and it is expectable since agriculture constitutes one of the most profitable economic activities. Further to this, waste from intensive livestock operations, poultry farms, pig farms, cattle farms and slaughterhouses are also considered biomass residues. Nevertheless, biomass does not produce heat on its own; it has to be processed to unlock its potential energy. Technically, via different thermal conversions, heat is used to process the biomass into a more usable fuel. One of the most common methods that is used, especially in the livestock sector, is the anaerobic digestion from which electrical power and heat can be produced from the biogas production. Livestock farmers (more often in dairy farms) use anaerobic digesters to produce biogas from manure and used bedding material. Moreover, they cover their manure holding ponds (also called manure lagoons) to capture biogas that forms in the lagoons. The methane in the biogas can be burned to heat water and buildings and as fuel in diesel-engine generators to generate electricity for the farm (Tursi, 2019; Morris, 2021).

3.1.6 Heat pumps

A heat pump is generally a device which is used to increase and sometimes decrease the temperature in buildings by transferring thermal energy from a cooler space to a warmer space using the refrigeration cycle, being the opposite direction in which heat transfer would take place without the application of external power. Heat pumps are often used in district heating systems and are considered as RES technologies due to their low energy consumption. When used for space heating, these devices are typically much more energy efficient than simple electrical resistance heaters. Moreover, they also have a lower carbon footprint than heating systems that burn fossil fuels such as natural gas, but those powered by hydrogen are also low-carbon and may become competitors. So far, heat pumps have been widely recognised as energy-efficient heating and cooling systems which have the potential to be combined with heat from other RES technologies in hybrid systems. According to the International Energy Agency more than 800 million heat pumps were installed, due to 2011, on Earth covering either domestic or industrial energy needs (Taylor, 2011).

In the framework of the livestock sector, heat pumps can be applied in all types of farms, either as a standalone technology or sometimes coupled with other RES systems like PVT. Common device types include air source heat pumps, ground source heat pumps, water source heat pumps and exhaust air heat pumps. The type and size of the animal farm can certainly have a significant effect on the size and the type of the heat pump, as well as its different functions, such as dehumidification and reheating. Of utmost importance is the kind of hosted animals as each kind, breed and age have different requirements. The energy profile of each farm should be thoroughly studied, considering - at least - the needed temperature (air and water) and humidity (Kharseh and Nordell, 2011; Akmesse, Omeroglu and Comakli, 2021).

3.2 Factors that influence RES involvement and efficiency

Despite the identification of all the aforementioned RES technologies as significant sources of energy for the whole livestock sector, in the past two decades the total amount dedicated to livestock

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

productivity remains insignificant compared to the amount allocated to the conventional energy sector. RES technologies have significant unexploited potential to enable farms to meet effectively and to a large extent their growing energy requirements. Nevertheless, their effectiveness is associated with a combination of factors which can be assessed with confidence to conclude whether a RES technology, or even an optimal combination of them, is/are capable to meet the needs of the respective livestock farm. The following factors are indicative:

- Position of the livestock building (e.g., location and orientation);
- Local environment (e.g., climate, elevation and slope, soil water, ground temperature, etc.);
- Characteristics of the buildings that constitute the farm unit (building insulation, existing of ventilation fans, etc.);
- Domestic needs of farm (e.g., high energy loads for milk cooling, air ventilation, management of the animals' by-products, etc.); and consumption profile (daily, seasonal).
- Planning policies for RES technologies in rural areas (Rota *et al.*, 2012).

In terms of energy consumption in a livestock farm, the effect of these factors is quite significant. According to different studies, the location and the orientation of the livestock building are both important in most cases, since they can determine which RES technology and in which place of the farm could potentially be applied thus increasing the efficiency and the livestock productivity. In the same line, the local climate (especially the climate and the ground temperature) as well as the construction method of the livestock farm can play a vital role that could potentially lead to a reduction in the final energy consumption of the livestock building.

This can be easily observed, especially in colder climates, where all the houses for pigs and poultry are insulated which means that losses of heat through walls, ceiling and floor are in many cases negligible. However, it should be noted that in these cases heat losses may occur due to the ventilation systems since these are responsible to remove moisture and gases from the animal house in order to provide a good environment for the animals (Horndahl, 2008).

Additionally, in many cases, farmers rely on the local conditions (local climate, existence of the soil water as well as the ground temperature) of the area of the farm but also on the experience of other farmers in order to choose that RES technology that they believe can bring them profits with low investment costs. The intrinsic requirements of each livestock farm along with the planning policies of the wider area can in turn be considered as important factors as well.

Past experience shows that the introduction and success of any RES technology, is inextricably linked to the existing government policy. Government policies are an important factor in terms of their ability to create an enabling environment for RES dissemination and mobilizing resources, as well as encouraging private sector investment (WEHAB Working Group, 2002).

3.3 Potential Applications

Considering all of the factors that can potentially affect the effectiveness of each RES in the selected livestock building, and especially these five factors that possess an essential role in most of the cases, it one can easily deduce that the final selection and installation of every renewable energy technology requires special attention.

It is clear that not all renewable energy sources can be placed on all types of farms so that all of their energy requirements are met through these. For instance, livestock farms in colder climates (e.g. Sweden or Norway), and especially pig houses have to be continually heated by an external heat

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

source for long periods and at the same time they have to be ventilated so that the relative humidity does not exceed 80% or the CO₂ content does not exceed 3,000 ppm (Horndahl, 2008).

This means that the exploitation of a geothermal heat pump or the utilization of wind and solar energy in alignment with a heat pump could theoretically be a fairly profitable and effective solution to the overall management of energy consumption of a livestock farm. Considering a similar farm located in a Mediterranean country where the percentage of solar radiation concentration is considerably higher -as is the air temperature- it is expected that farm owners will first consider the exploitation of the solar energy through PV/PVT panels as it is presented in the following schematic (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Schematic illustration of a basic PV system for a swine farm (Green et al., 2002).

However, it should be mentioned that in some cases the selection of the renewable energy technology depends on a combination of the aforementioned factors as well as on the type of livestock unit (dairy, pig, poultry farms) and the specific requirements that arise from it. To elaborate, in the case of a bovine farm, the reduction of the total energy needs is of high interest independently from the location of the farm. Clearly the location and orientation of the livestock building contribute to the final energy consumptions, however, the energy bills are so high that farm owners often have to consider alternatives that could potentially combine more than one RES technology. In that case, owners should consider which RES technology could fit to the energy needs arising from the ventilation and heating needs to the manure handling and feeding processes that dairy farms include.

Moreover, dairy farms spend a significant percentage of their overall energy consumption within milk production stages, since energy is used for milk cooling and a lot of it is also required to power vacuum pumps. A useful solution in such cases consists of the exploitation of the biogas production coming from the vast amounts of manure that is annually produced in this farm (especially in areas with extensive grassland and arable crops, which in terms produce residual biomass allocated either as animal feed or as fuel for biomass boilers) and could be probably used as raw material or as bio-fertilizer in the same arable areas.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

4 MOST PROMISING RES TECHNOLOGIES AND EFFICIENCY MEASURES FOR LIVESTOCK FARMS

Following the information presented in previous Sections, it is evident that Renewable Energy Sources are increasingly gaining attention as a sustainable energy source in the livestock farm sector (Chel and Kaushik, 2011), under specific circumstances and energy needs. At first glance, one might think that all renewable energy sources can be used efficiently in all types of farms. However, as mentioned before and according to Firfiris et al. (Firfiris, Martzopoulou and Kotsopoulos, 2019), efficiency is affected by various decision making factors, which are also those that finally indicate which RES technologies are the most promising for the livestock farms.

Following the same logic, numerous publications present have studied and determined the energy flow among various operations in a livestock farm. They also attempted to estimate how the replacement of some conventional technologies with renewable ones contributed to the final energy reduction in different livestock farms around the world. Taking advantage of the results acquired from all the studies, pioneer farmers have managed to integrate various RES technologies into their farms, greatly reducing their dependence from fossil fuels and making their farms more environmentally friendly. These cases (some of which will be presented below), constitute the examples showcasing that if renewable energy sources are properly dimensioned and combined, they can perform to the fullest.

One of the most remarkable examples is the case of a small wooden windmill in Groningen, the Netherlands, which is incredibly popular and is being used by hundreds of farmers in the country. The idea for the windmills originated on a farmyard in Groningen, when one of the five founders, Sjouke Ritsema, built the first windmill for his father, but the neighbors turned out to like it too. The windmill supplies the farmers with energy whenever they need it and can be combined with solar panels and thus supply them with energy all year around (*Small, wooden windmill from Groningen incredibly popular: 'Farmers down the road want one too' - Innovation Origins*, no date). In the same line, a cattle farm in Lugo, Milan, manages food, milking and breeding for more than 150 livestock through robotic and fully automatic systems. The farm works entirely with wind and solar power in a mixed system that provides more than 120 kWh daily, with a peak power of about 40 kW. The use of solar and wind technology keeps the generation flow constant both night and day, saving the surplus in batteries that are used to meet the energy needs when the renewable resource is not enough. This livestock installation constitutes a benchmark in the market, since apart from the automatic management and computerized control of the farm, the main goal is to keep the electrical expenditure of this installation practically zero (*Sustainable Livestock industry*, no date).

Another indicative example is the Tauwitchere Dairy, located near the Coorong in Narrung South-East South Australia ('Saving energy on dairy farms', 2013), which installed a 60 kW solar PV system and managed to minimize the impact of the increased retailer rates (by saving \$1,275 per month). Yeowood Solar Farm in North Somerset is one of the many cases in the United Kingdom that focused on solar energy and managed to increase the annual income by minimizing the outcomes. This farm's owners completed in 2012 a 1.3 MW installation on 4 ha of land surrounding a poultry farm of 24,000 laying hens, which are free to roam the land between and underneath the rows of solar modules, as well as other fields (Scurlock, 2014). An additional case study is a broiler farm in Lincolnshire, UK. It's a large-scale commercial farm which has 4 new poultry sheds to house 200,000 animals in total. The heating demands of this farm were extremely high and the farm owner was therefore looking for a system that would deliver cost-effective heating to combat rising energy costs. For that reason, it was considered that the only obvious solution was to install a heat pump

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

system (1.2 MW) that could deliver 4x times the heat output for every kilowatt of electricity used to power it. The heat pumps, underfloor heating and radiators not only guarantee efficient heating, but also provide the sheds with passive cooling which in turn removes excess heat from the sheds via the underfloor pipework and fan coils (IPT Technology Ltd, no date).

It is also worth mentioning that an investigation of the effect of a heating system using a Geothermal Heat Pump (GHP) on production performance and housing environment of broiler chickens in Korea showed that the total energy cost of heating the GHP house was significantly lower compared with that of the conventional house (Choi *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, it is concluded that GHP may have environmental benefits with the effective and economic heating and cooling on swine houses as well. Finally, yet importantly, is the case of a broiler house in Korea for which is designed, developed and tested a small-scale wind turbine fitted to the ventilation fan. This system finally concluded that there is an increased economic assistance in the final energy costs (savings) despite the fact that there was a 1.5% ventilation rate reduction (Hong *et al.*, 2013).

All the above examples confirm the fact that there is indeed a “penetration potential” of RES technologies in the livestock sector but it was deemed necessary to take a closer look at each of these technologies separately in order to better classify the most promising RES based on the livestock farm type.

4.1 Solar Energy Applications

As mentioned before, solar energy is broadly categorized into (a) solar photovoltaic (PV) technologies and (b) solar thermal technologies. The solar thermal panels, typically abbreviated as PVT collectors and known as hybrid solar collector panels, convert the solar energy into heat and electricity, contrary to the solar photovoltaic collectors, which convert it directly into electricity. PVT collectors combine photovoltaic solar cells, which convert sunlight into electricity, with a solar thermal collector, which transfers the otherwise unused excess heat from the PV module to a heat transfer fluid. By combining electricity and heat generation within the same component, these technologies can reach a higher overall efficiency than solar photovoltaic (PV) or solar thermal alone. The main purpose of using this technology is to get hot water or hot air for heating/cooling applications (Al-Waeli *et al.*, 2017).

Solar energy can generally cover a wide range of applications. PV systems can provide supplemental power source for homes, businesses, municipalities and can be the primary power source for remote systems, while solar thermal technologies can be used in domestic or industrial level, covering both heating and cooling purposes (swimming pool heating, solar underfloor heating, domestic hot water, solar heat for industries, refrigeration, and air conditioning). In the agriculture field, solar energy in the form of PV systems may be the most cost-effective water pumping option in locations where there is no existing power line, while PVT collectors can be used in large greenhouses as a source of heat in the ground and electricity for the fans.

However, in the livestock sector, there is little documentation for the use of PVT in livestock farming. This could be explained by the fact that conventional PVT systems are typically operated below 100 °C, which prevents their application to industrial and agricultural processes where higher temperature heat is needed. One way to overcome this is to combine the PVT with heat pumps. Furthermore, a promising solution to tackle this limitation is to split the incident solar spectrum into two separate bands, one that is directed to PV modules and is well-suited to conversion into electricity, while the rest is absorbed as heat by a thermal absorber (Kalogirou, 2004; Lämmle, Herrando and Ryan, 2020).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Essentially, solar energy technologies can be exploited in all types of farms covering both electricity and heating needs. Nevertheless, PVT systems are a technology that is commonly applied in all type of farms since they have the ability to cover the extremely high thermal and heating needs created in livestock buildings, in contrast with PV systems can be effectively applied in remote farms where there is no existing power grid, but it is not suggested for large commercial farms (Diwania *et al.*, 2020).

On the other hand, PVT systems along with a couple of a heat pump or a small wind turbine may consist one of the most promising RES combination in the livestock sector since it is possible to produce electricity from solar thermal energy systems. Solar hot water systems are recommended for dairy farms to cover the energy needs required for the heating water purposes.

Moreover, according to literature data, it has been observed that the combination of a PVT system with a heat pump can also cover the energy needs for the milk cooling purposes as well as the lighting needs of the building. Concerning the pig farms where more than 50% of the energy needs refereed to the heat farrowing and post-weaning units a PVT system is recommended as the most promising one to cover these needs ('Saving energy on dairy farms', 2013).

As for the poultry sector, some entrepreneurs have started to implement the use of photovoltaic solar energy for poultry production farms. This type of renewable energy is the most common in this sector. The use of lighting can artificially extend the day, increase the growth of poultry and the production of eggs. Another important factor for poultry farms in some areas is the heat, necessary for the reduction of the mortality rate of pullets. In conventional poultry farms heat lamps/lights are used to provide both heat and light. In hot areas, ventilation is needed, which can more easily be supplied with PV-powered electric fans (Cui, Xue and Riffat, 2021).

However, the impact of the local climate on the performance of PVT collectors is very important. Factors like the given solar radiation of a location, the local air temperature, the geometry and orientation/inclination of the collector and the possible sources of shadings must be taken under consideration before the installation of a PVT system.

4.2 Bioenergy Applications

Bioenergy is the main renewable energy form worldwide, making up about 70% of all primary renewable energy sources (International Energy Agency, 2016). Bioenergy is the energy extracted from organic matter of plant or animal origin, also known as biomass, such as agricultural and forest residues, energy crops, wood, or organic wastes. Due to its high flexibility for integration into a wide of energy systems, bioenergy is a highly attractive energy option for countries at all stages of development (CERTH/CPERI, 2020). Generally, bioenergy can be used to generate electricity, heat or transport fuel, as well and solid, liquid and gaseous energy carriers. It is therefore a promising RES technology for all types of farms especially in large grassland and arable areas.

Bioenergy systems can be easily integrated into existing energy infrastructures, technologies, and applications, while they can also be a waste management solution; as organic waste and especially wood-based materials provide valuable feedstock. Using anaerobic digestion for treating and managing livestock manures and slurry and organic waste (mainly food) is a long-established application. Usually, bioenergy systems are aligned with ORC (Organic Rankine Cycle) technologies aiming to optimize the produced energy (Röder and Thornley, 2018).

Although bioenergy has long been the main renewable energy source (60%), with heating and cooling the largest end-users of bioenergy (75%), there are some factors that affect its wide implementation, including concerns about land use, crop usage, energy efficiency, and cost. Other

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

concerns about bioenergy include food security, deforestation and loss of biodiversity, animal capacities and available spaces in the farms. This makes perfect sense as according to various reports it is extremely difficult for a livestock farm (especially for diaries and pig farms) to meet its thermal needs solely by using bioenergy.

4.3 Applications of Heat Pumps

The term heat pump (HP) refers to a device used for extracting heat from low temperature surroundings and sending it to high temperature space or system, while operating a cycle. Therefore, the working principle of a heat pump is based on the reversed Carnot cycle, also called refrigeration cycle. A heat pump is not a work producing machine, while its objective is to maintain a body at higher temperature, so its performance cannot be defined using efficiency as in case of heat engine. Instead, the Coefficient Of Performance (COP) is used, defined as the ratio of useful heating or cooling provided to work (energy) required. COP takes usually values greater than 1 while the higher the COP is, the more efficient a heat pump is and the less energy it consumes.

Nowadays, heat pump is considered as a RES technology due to its low energy consumption. In general, the design of a heat pump is affected by the heat source (e.g., air, ground, solar). The components' dimensions, as well as the overall size of the heat pump, depend on the specifications that have to be met. Depending on the application, heat pumps can be combined with heat from other RES technologies in hybrid systems. These sources might be renewable in origin or waste energy from industrial processes and exhaust air from buildings. Heat pumps can be highly efficient, although their overall primary energy efficiency depends on the efficiency of the electricity production (or other thermal energy source) they use. The most common heat sources are the ambient air and the ground.

Moreover, the heat pumps can be combined with photovoltaic systems or other waste heat sources (WHR), which can provide heat to the heat pump's evaporator. Heat pumps have long been widely recognised as energy-efficient heating and cooling systems and have been proposed for greenhouse heating since the early 1970's. However, due to their low COP and high cost of installation, they were not reconsidered as an alternative heating system until the rise of energy costs and their technical advancement.

In the livestock sector, dairy-related energy saving applications include milk cooling and water heating on farms for cleaning of tools and equipment, but also off-farm pasteurization. Exclusive on-farm applications, especially in confined poultry and pig building, are also present in literature. Heat recovery applications have been theoretically investigated during the last decades in pig farm facilities, and the use of Ground Source Heat Pump (GSHP) has been tested. In the case of broiler houses, work has been done on modelling different systems, such as HVAC systems for precise environment control in Greece, and ground-coupled heating/cooling system for typical chicken farm in Syria. The coupling of PVT/heat pump system has also been experimentally investigated and monitored. It is evident that in the scientific community, there is great interest towards applications where the heat pumps also coupled with geothermal energy and PV/Ts that especially in poultry and pig facilities (confined animal buildings) (Ubbels and Bouman, 1979; Jordan *et al.*, 2016; Akmese, Omeroglu and Comakli, 2021).

When calculating financial viability, the offset cost of an alternative heating system -such as a gas boiler- should also be considered. Heat pumps look much more viable where there is a cooling demand, and their capital cost can be spread over the heating and cooling savings, resulting a faster payback (Caslin *et al.*, 2011). Of course, in the framework of livestock industry interventions, other

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

factors -such as reduced medication, feed consumption, mortality, and quality enhancement- shall also be considered.

4.4 Geothermal Energy Applications

Geothermal energy technologies consider all technologies that use the soil for energy-related applications. A distinction is made between shallow and deep geothermal systems, since deep systems make use of the rising soil temperature at greater depths (> 500 m), while shallow systems make use of the natural and constant temperature at a depth between 10 and 150 m. This temperature fluctuates between 5 °C in the extreme north to 20 °C in the extreme south of Europe. The aim of deep geothermal applications is to extract high-temperature heat (> 120 °C) at great depths for electricity production (high-enthalpic applications) or medium-temperature heat (< 120 °C) for direct heating (low-enthalpic applications). Shallow systems (limited to a depth of 150 to 250 m) can be further divided into different categories. There are the heat extraction systems, energy storage systems and Earth-to-Air Heat Exchangers (EAHE), also known as Canadian Wells.

Regardless of the applied geothermal technology (ATES – Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage or BTES – Borehole Thermal Energy Storage), different energy concepts can be developed. Geothermal energy systems can be used for all livestock applications where there is a need for heating and/or cooling, regardless of the farm type. Of course, a delivery system should also be present, but this might take one of several forms (Alberti *et al.*, 2018). Farm buildings can use geothermal heat pumps to exchange air temperature and ground temperature year-round, keeping buildings cool in summer and warm in winter.

Geothermal energy is preferable in dairy and pig farms since it can restore variable heating and cooling needs. However, the application of geothermal systems and concepts must be investigated per climate zone. The available average temperature of the subsurface fluctuates greatly from northern to southern Europe, which means that certain concepts are better/less suitable. For example, natural cooling is more difficult to apply in southern European countries when natural ground temperatures are higher than 15 °C (e.g. Mediterranean countries such as Spain, Italy or Greece).

4.5 Wind Energy Applications

Wind energy is renewable and widely available, while its generation process is “clean” without producing greenhouse gases. The wind energy can be harnessed through a wind turbine and transformed into electrical power or mechanical work. Based on the output power, the wind turbine is catalogued as small (300 W to 100 kW), medium (100 kW to 1 MW) or large (>1 MW), while based on the structure, wind turbines could be divided into horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) and vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) (Song, Kang and Hahm, 2003).

According to literature data, the wind turbine could be either installed standalone in open areas or integrated with building (e.g., installed at walls or roof-top). For the implementation in livestock farm, installing the wind turbine stand-alone in open areas away from the buildings is preferred for maximum energy harness. The conversion of available wind power into actual power varies nonlinearly due to the transfer functions of the electrical generators. Besides wind condition, icing condition needed to be considered when installing wind turbine in high altitudes and arctic latitudes, e.g. Finland (Laakso *et al.*, 2010). Ice accretion on turbine blades can degrade turbine performance and durability, and even lead to safety concerns associated with ice shedding (if ice were thrown from the rotating blades).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

The implementation of wind turbines in livestock farming is well adaptable to the type of farm, since they can be installed stand-alone away from the livestock building. However, the impact of the generated by the wind turbines noise on the productivity of animal needs to be evaluated before their implementation. Meanwhile, the implementation of wind turbines could not affect the present power and heat (or cooling) delivery system, since they are implemented as assistant energy supply and not directly connected to present power systems. Nevertheless, wind energy could potentially cover wide range of energy needs starting from the ventilation systems and fans, and concluding on all the systems that require electrical energy (lighting, humidity control – especially in poultry farms, feed delivery and mixing in pig farms, manure pumps to mix and agitate slurry tanks in all types of farms, and more). It is worth mentioning that wind energy constitutes one of the most promising RES technologies, especially in poultry and pig farms, since the electricity demands for ventilation systems and lighting are of high interest.

4.6 ORC Applications

The Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) engine refers to a device that utilizes low-temperature heat to convert it into useful work, which can subsequently be converted into electrical energy, while operating in a cycle. Conceptually, the ORC is similar to a Steam Rankine Cycle, but a refrigerant (organic fluid) is used as working fluid instead of water, and it is based on the vaporization of a high-pressure liquid, which in turn is expanded to a lower pressure, producing electrical work. ORC systems can utilize heat from many different sources at heat supply temperatures ranging between 80 to 200 °C. These sources might be renewable in origin or waste energy from industrial processes and components: biomass, geothermal, waste heat recovery, and solar.

ORC unit is frequently used in small scale applications in alignment with steam engines, gasification systems with the possibility of hot air and Sterling engines. These systems can be fitted in all types of farms providing both power and heat from the same produced by-products (manure, sludge, solid biomass). The efficiency of current high temperature Organic Rankine Cycles does not exceed 24%. At low temperatures, its efficiency is usually in the range of 4-6% (up to 10-12% for specific applications), but still there are cases where it can be cost effective, especially for waste heat recovery thus improving the overall process/system energy efficiency (Kosmadakis, Manolakos and Papadakis, 2016). At this point, it is worth noting that heat recovery systems could be a useful solution for all types of farms in order to cover the energy needs required for the water heating.

Nevertheless, the on-farm use of an ORC unit is still relatively uncommon despite the fact that dry biomass (wood chips, wood pellets, agro-pellets, grass etc.) is widely used as heat source in combined projects in which ORC acts as heat and power unit where all heat delivered to the machine is recovered (*Biomass CHP | E-RATIONAL*, no date). Furthermore, it should be noted that there are several ORC installations in biogas plants, where ORC engine is coupled with the ICE cooling water circuit to increase thermal efficiency by about 5%. These ORC units can recover low grade heat from jacket cooling and/or exhaust gas cooling and transform it into cost-effective electricity (*Stationary Engines | E-RATIONAL*, no date).

Summarizing the information presented above, past experience and relevant literature both indicate that the most promising RES technologies are solar and wind systems in combination with heat pumps and ORC units basically applied in biogas plants and possibly low temperature geothermal systems. These technologies have the potential to be applied to all types of farms, covering an extremely wide range of energy requirements. Moreover, geothermal energy units have also a great

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

potential in the livestock sector since they have the ability to store the excess energy produced and to provide it to the system when needed.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

5 EXISTING SITUATION OF PILOT LIVESTOCK FARMS – ENERGY AUDITS

5.1 Energy Audits as an Energy Efficiency tool

In 2007, the EU leaders set 3 key targets for 2020: (a) 20% cut in greenhouse emissions from the 1990 levels, (b) 20% of EU energy to derive from RES and (c) 20% improvement in energy efficiency. The last was enacted with the 2012 Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU) (*EUR-Lex - 32012L0027 - EN - EUR-Lex*, no date), which established a set of binding measures to help the EU reach its goal. Under that Directive, the Member States of the EU are obliged to utilize energy more efficiently at all stages of the energy chain. Article 8 sets out requirements for Member States to promote the availability of energy audits⁴ to all final energy users including households, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and non-SMEs. More specifically, some key points in the Directive are:

Article 8(2) establishes that Member States shall develop programmes to encourage SMES undergo energy audits and the subsequent implementation of the recommendations from these audits.

Article 8(4) establishes that Member States must ensure that enterprises that are not SMEs are subject to an energy audit by December 12th, 2015, and at least every 4 years from the date of the previous energy audit.

Article 8(1) states that for the purpose of guaranteeing the high quality of the energy audits and energy management systems, Member States shall establish transparent and non-discriminatory minimum criteria for energy audits based on Annex VI. As such, Annex VI of the Directive issues the following guidelines:

- (a) The energy audits shall be based on up-to-date, measured, traceable operational data on energy consumption and (for electricity) load profiles;
- (b) Shall comprise a detailed review of the energy consumption profile of buildings or groups of buildings, industrial operation or installations, including transportation;
- (c) Shall be build, whenever possible, on life-cycle cost analysis (LCCA) instead of Simple Payback Periods (SPP) in order to take account of long-term savings, residual values of long-term investments and discount rates;
- (d) Shall be proportionate, and sufficiently representative to permit the drawing of a reliable picture of overall energy performance and the reliable identification of the most significant opportunities for improvement.

Additionally, energy audits shall allow detailed and validated calculations for the proposed measures so as to provide clear information on potential savings. The data used in energy audits shall be storable for historical analysis and tracking performance.

The minimum criteria of Annex VI have been put in place to support the requirements of Article 8, such that:

- (a) Energy audits are of high-quality.

⁴ According to Article 2(25) of the Directive 2012/27/EU, “energy audit” means a systematic procedure with the purpose of obtaining adequate knowledge of the existing energy consumption profile of a building or group of buildings, an industrial or commercial operation or installation or a private or public service, identifying and quantifying cost-effective energy savings opportunities, and reporting the findings.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

- a. Based on transparent and non-discriminatory criteria (Annex VI).
- b. The quality of the energy audits and similar measures is supervised.
 - (b) Energy audits are cost-effective.
 - (c) Energy audits are undertaken in an independent manner.
 - (d) Their findings are transferrable.

According to ('Energy Savings Potential in Cyprus Subsectors: Floriculture and vegetables in greenhouses The Cyprus energy profile for the greenhouses sector: current situation and energy saving measures in combination with RES Deliverable 3.1', 2017), energy audit approaches vary in terms of scope, aim and thoroughness and can generally be categorized into:

- Level I. Walk-through energy audit: Walk-through energy audit provides energy consumptions costs and energy efficiency data based on energy bills and the results of a short autopsy. This inspection is based on visual verifications, study of installed equipment and operating data and detailed analysis of recorded energy consumption. A candidate list of interventions or investment is provided which need further examination together with the preliminary estimations of the potential costs and the corresponding benefit.
- Level II. Comprehensive energy audit: This type of energy audit consists in energy use survey in order to provide a comprehensive analysis of the studied installation, a more detailed analysis of the facility, a breakdown of the energy use and a first quantitative evaluation of the interventions and investment selected to correct the defects or improve the existing installation. This level of analysis can involve advanced on-site measurements and computer-based simulation tools to precisely evaluate the selected energy efficiency measures.
- Level III. Detailed energy audit: The detailed energy audit (energy study) includes a detailed analysis of capital-intensive modifications focusing on potential costly interventions and investments requiring rigorous engineering studies.

According to the Final Report of the Smart Integrated Livestock Farming (SILF) Project which concluded in 2016 (*Smart Integrated Livestock Farming: integrating user-centric & ICT-based decision support platform | ICT-AGRI-FOOD Meta Knowledge Base*, no date), a typical energy audit process description includes: (a) site visit, (b) collection of data, (c) measurements and recording, (d) processing of the collected data, (e) calculation of energy indices, (d) comparison and allocation of the (i) high energy demanding equipment and processes and (ii) inefficient energy equipment and process and (g) proposals for improvement of energy consumption.

For livestock buildings specifically, the energy audit composition has not yet been addressed at European level and in this sense, it can be treated with a combination of methods used for conventional buildings and industrial applications.

For the record, in December 2018 the amended Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2018/2002 (*EUR-Lex - 32018L2002 - EN - EUR-Lex*, no date) entered into force. Besides updating some specific provisions from the previous Directive, it also introduces several new elements. Above all, it establishes a headline EU energy efficiency target for 2030 of at least 32.5% (compared to projections of the expected energy use in 2030), with a clause for potential (upwards) revision by 2023. According to the Regulation on the governance of the energy union and climate action (EU)2018/1999 (*EUR-Lex - 32018R1999 - EN - EUR-Lex*, no date), each EU country is required to establish a 10-year integrated national energy and climate plan (*National energy and climate plans | European Commission*, no date) for 2021-2030, outlining how it intends to contribute to the 2030 energy efficiency, renewable energy and greenhouse gas emissions targets.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

5.2 Methodology of data collection

The main purpose of this work was to give a first, representative picture of the current situation in terms of energy demands/consumption in the 4 pilot farms and more specifically, in the buildings of interest. In all 4 cases the data was collected having as a reference point the buildings of interest, meaning the specific buildings that in the context of RES4LIVE interventions are foreseen, and not the farms as whole units⁵.

Initially, descriptions and schematics of the buildings were requested, from which the buildings' dimensions, construction materials, openings (doors and windows), insulation (if existing) and intended usage (animal type and population) were derived. The purpose of having this data is double as by knowing the above characteristics: (a) the thermal losses of each -enclosed- building can be estimated and by extension the amount of heat that should be provided inside the building to maintain the desired temperature, and (b) it effectively acts as preparatory work for Task 3.4 as it provides an initial input to the simulation tool in order to assess the percentage of energy requirements that could be covered with RES. For buildings like the ones selected in the pilot farm in Italy (Gollineli commercial farm), due to limited available data, the estimation of the thermal losses assisted in the calculation of the energy demand of the specific buildings, as explained in [Section 5.3.2](#).

Then, the energy consumption details were collected and depicted in dedicated MS Office Excel Worksheets. The classification of the consumption data was carried out in 4 levels of detail, as follows:

- **1st level:** At the first level consumptions are separated based on the different types of energy (electrical, diesel fuel, biogas, natural gas).
- **2nd level:** At the second level each of the previous consumption data per energy type -where existing- is filled in for each specific building of interest.
- **3rd level:** At the third level the consumptions are assigned to specific devices/device types.
- **4th level:** The fourth level represents the devices' working time in hours per month, for a full year cycle.

Third and fourth levels were not addressed for every building/consumption as in some cases data was insufficient and the estimations would not be accurate.

Additionally, monthly feed distribution (kg of feed per animal and feed type; per month) and milk production data (kg per month; for the dairy farm) were calculated for each specific building, where possible. Feed intake and milk production may not be directly connected to the on-farm energy consumption, but they are heavily related to the thermal comfort of the animals⁶ (Bouraoui *et al.*, 2002) which is affected by energy consumers and thus, it was deemed useful to also record this data in the context of assessing the existing situation of the pilot farms. This data is not displayed in the current document but can be shared after communication.

⁵ It should be noted that due to the restrictions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic during the data gathering period, it was not possible to arrange a visit in the 3 out of 4 farms in order to get a better understanding of their layout, neither to assist in the gathering of the required data. Thus, relevant Partners undertook both the tasks of (a) explaining the farms' infrastructures to the interested Partners through online meetings and (b) ensuring the accurate gathering of all the data required.

⁶ In example, in case of heat stress due to higher than air temperatures, pigs will reduce their heat production by lowering their activity and feed intake (Godyń *et al.*, 2020).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Apart from the initial questionnaire, additional contacts with the pilot farms and the relevant Partners secured the gathering of the necessary data.

Given that without specific sensors installed to collect the required data, most calculations were based on existing invoices of the farms (and/or mains meters). Each farms' available data was ranging in different levels of detail. As expected, that led to compulsory deviations and assumptions as deemed necessary.

5.3 Existing situation of pilot farms

This paragraph is dedicated to the depiction of the current status of the 4 pilot farms according to the methodology described in [Section 5.2](#). All available consumption data is presented in a comprehensible way and is preceded by a short description of each farm. Buildings' details, feed and milk data are not delivered in this report. For the raw data please contact the authors who will be able to assist you in consultation with the pilot farms.

5.3.1 Pilot farm in Belgium (swine)

The experimental farm "Varkenscampus" in Melle, Flanders Belgium is managed by EV ILVO, UGENT and HoGent both for research/educational purposes, and normal commercial production. It's a farrow-to-finish pig farm which utilizes a 3-week management cycle system. Its average occupancy, based on 2020 data, is:

- 110 sows,
- 366 piglets,
- 463 fattening pigs,
- 9 young sows and
- 2 boars.

The farm consists of 2 main buildings, which are however linked to each other by a corridor, a wall and a common ceiling and were thus considered as a single (Building 1) for the purposes of this audit ([Figure 6](#)).

Figure 6. (a) ILVO farm, outside view and (b) plain schematic of the two sections with the common ceiling.

The total building area is 2,550 m² (Section A: 1,199 m², Section B: 1180 m²) and contains mainly concrete and insulation with polypropylene panels dividing the compartments and partially slatted concrete floors above the manure pits. More specifically, the farms' compartments and places are as follows:

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

- 2 farrowing compartments, with 16 places for sows each,
- 1 insemination compartment with 40 places,
- 1 gestating sow compartment with 64 places,
- 3 nurseries, with 192 places for piglets each,
- 16 fattening pigs compartments, with 40 places for pigs each,
- 1 quarantine pen with 12 places for young sows and
- 1 boar pen with 2 places for boars.

The total estimated **annual** energy consumption per energy type, as recorded in previous years' data is aggregated to:

- Electrical energy: **115,000 kWh** (2020) utilized for:
 - Lighting (200 LED lamps),
 - Heating (32 thermal lamps in the farrowing compartment, 3 circulation pumps),
 - Ventilation (6 pressure fans, 8 DC fans in the farrowing compartment),
 - Various engines/pumps (Air washers, Feeding system, Water, High pressure cleaner).
- Natural gas: **21,773 m³** (2020) utilized for heating through an ATAG natural gas condensing boiler of 60 kW (Air heating, Floor heating, Sanitary warm water), which results in about 220,000 kWh of energy. Data was acquired from meter readings.
- Fuel oil: **916 L** (2020) utilized for heating through a heat canon periodically and mainly during the cold months. The heat canon's average consumption varies between 40 to 80 L/3 days, depending on the ambient temperature. The consumption was estimated on a season basis. In winter the heat canon is being used 1 week every 3 weeks to heat the newcomer pigs of ~25 kg. In autumn and spring, it is used about 1 day every 3 weeks and in summer only for a few hours in total.

In the following figures the allocations of the different consumptions in a 12-month cycle are being showcased.

Figure 7. ILVO farm's electrical energy consumption allocation throughout a year (2020).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Figure 8. ILVO farm's natural gas consumption allocation throughout a year (2020).

Figure 9. ILVO farm's fuel oil consumption allocation throughout a year (2020).

It can be observed that the fluctuation of the electrical energy consumption in [Figure 7](#) is perceivable, but limited; in contrast with the natural gas ([Figure 8](#)) and the fuel oil ([Figure 9](#)) which are mainly used in the colder months. That is due to the fact that in this specific farm the electrical energy is only a fraction of the energy utilized for heating (for the heat lamps) and thus, there is no peak in the colder months. The main heating system is the gas boiler supported -under conditions- by the heat canon and for that reason their consumptions sharply increase during the colder periods.

5.3.2 Pilot farm in Italy (swine)

The second pilot pig farm is the commercial farm GOLINELLI, located in the Modena province, Italy. Its occupancy varies in about 500 sows and 2,500 weaners and consists of a farrowing barn, a nursery barn, a gestation barn, and a hog (sow) barn with a gestation sector. The buildings cover an area of about 3,800 m² and, except for the latter (hog barn), they are made of precast reinforced concrete with thermal insulation ([Figure 10](#)).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

(a)

(b)

Figure 10. (a) GOLINELLI farm building 12, outside view and (b) general layout plan of the farm.

The buildings which are of interest for the RES4LIVE Project are:

- Building 12: a hog barn of 663 m² area to rear 400 sows and
- Building 16: a nursery barn of 1,002 m² area for 2,400 weaners allocated in 10 spaces (240 weaners per space).

For the particular buildings, all structural characteristics were recorded in detail. However, as previously mentioned, the available consumption data for the GOLINELLI farm was very limited, and estimations had to be done in order to acquire an adequate picture per building of interest in this first approach. Limited data is mainly because GOLINELLI farm is a commercial farm -the only commercial farm among the pilots- and thus such data is not readily available. At this stage, the known data was used as an input to a computational analysis software (ANSYS Steady-State Thermal Solver) and the temperature distribution / thermal flows were calculated. At the next phase (Deliverable 3.5 – M24/CERTH) these calculations will be improved upon and then validated/compared to the measured data, which will be acquired through the sensors installed in the context of RES4LIVE Task 3.3.

Building 12 is heated by an LPG boiler of 115 kW. Building 16's main corridor is heated by a 34 kW LPG boiler through finned tubes (Water temp: 70 °C), while each distinct space is heated by 5 thermal lamps of 1500 kW each. Ventilation is achieved through an extraction fan and windows' opening.

Simulations were conducted for both buildings. For the simulations, the thermal (heat) loads of the animals⁷, the desired temperatures in each space, the ambient temperature and the building's details were utilized, and the visualized results are presented below.

⁷ Heat load in livestock: Metabolic heat produced during digestion and metabolism of food.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

(a) Building 12 for ambient temperature of 3 °C (Colour scale in Kelvin)

(b) Building 12 for ambient temperature of 15 °C

(c) Building 12 for ambient temperature of 28 °C

Figure 11. Temperature distribution (colour coded scalar field) and thermal flows (vector field) in GOLINELLI farm Building 12 for three different ambient temperatures.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

(a) Building 16 for ambient temperature of 3 °C (Colour scale in Kelvin)

(b) Building 16 for ambient temperature of 15 °C

(c) Building 16 for ambient temperature of 28 °C

Figure 12. Temperature distribution (colour coded scalar field) and thermal flows (vector field) in GOLINELLI farm Building 16 for three different ambient temperatures.

In the above figures, colours represent the temperature gradient and the arrows the conductive heat flux. The ambient temperature data is based on historical weather data of the region which ranges from 2 to 24 °C average per month. Two outliers (min/max) and an average value for the ambient

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

temperature have been depicted as shown in the captions. From the above simulations the heat transfer coefficients of the two buildings can be derived⁸:

- Building 12: 13.62 kWh/K,
- Building 16: 43.53 kWh/K.

In [Figure 13](#) and [Figure 14](#) the monthly energy requirements are calculated for a full year period. The positive values represent the energy requirements (in kWh) for heating, while the negative values (in summer months) for cooling. In other words, negative sign does not imply an energy profit, but energy requirements for cooling.

Figure 13. Yearly allocation of the energy requirements for temperature control in Building 12 of GOLINELLI farm.

Figure 14. Yearly allocation of the energy requirements for temperature control in Building 16 of GOLINELLI farm.

A conclusion that can be drawn from the figures above is that the energy requirements of Building 16 will be significantly higher than those of Building 12 over a year. This difference in energy demand for climate control can be attributed to the lack of thermal insulation within the walls of Building 16, the large number of windows (72) which contribute to heat losses and the overall dimensions of the building itself.

⁸ How much energy should be consumed in order to raise the internal temperature by 1 degree Kelvin (K).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

- Diesel: **13,900 L** utilized for dairy management (a wheel loader and a tractor).
- Biogas: the heat generated by biogas is utilized for heating the office buildings and thus, was not taken under consideration. The farm utilizes a biogas power plant of 696 kW thermal. The slurry leaves the barn and is heated to 40 °C for the digestion process. The outflow to the office and guesthouse buildings sums up to about 200 MW heat annually (approx. 25,000 L).

Figure 16. Breakdown of LVAT farm's electrical energy demand.

In [Figure 17](#) is imprinted the allocation of the electrical energy consumption in a typical year, per building of interest. Detailed data regarding the monthly consumption per device is also available. In summary, the overall annual electric energy consumption of each separate building is estimated as follows:

- Barn 1: 205,069 kWh
- Barn 2: 15,101 kWh
- Barn 29: 56,307 kWh

It can be observed that for both barns 1 and 29 the consumption grows higher during the summer months. The main cause for this variation is the energy consumed from the electric fans for ventilation purposes. The fans will start operating when the temperature rises above 15 °C and as observed also in [Figure 16](#), are responsible for a large percentage of the electrical energy consumption in this pilot farm.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Figure 17. Electrical energy consumption of LVAT's farm per barn.

As mentioned previously, LPG in LVAT farm is utilized for heating the working areas related to milk production and is estimated to 30,000 kWh per annum. LPG heating is applied mainly in the winter period, in barns 1 and 29. More details regarding the allocation are visible in Figure 18. The consumption is displayed in litres/month. The allocation of the consumption per specific need is depicted only for Barn 1 (B1. "usage"); with magenta colour is depicted the aggregation of the 3 separate "B1." entries as "Barn 1 (total)"; and in light blue the total consumption of Barn 29. As expected, apart from some room heating needs of Barn 1 during the colder months of spring/autumn, the main consumption occurs from December to February, for both barns.

Figure 18. LPG consumption of LVAT's farm per barn and usage.

Out of the 13,900 L of Diesel fuel consumed annually in LVAT farm, it is estimated that about 6,000 L are demanded for the dairy management of the 3 buildings of interest. The fuel is used by a wheel loader (for manure management) and a tractor, and the workload/consumption is evenly distributed throughout the year as it concerns constant tasks. For the most accurate estimation of the

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

distribution of the consumption between Barns 1, 2 and 29; the livestock unit (LU) reference unit was utilized⁹. For grown cows $LU_{cow} = 1$ was defined, while for young cattle $LU_{youngcattle} = 0.6$. Therefore, for each building the annual diesel fuel consumption is presented in Figure 19 and is calculated as follows:

- Barn 1: $6,000 L \times ((135 \times 1) + (15 \times 1)) \div 300 = 3,000 L$
- Barn 2: $6,000 L \times ((55 \times 1) + (15 \times 0.6)) \div 300 = 1,280 L$
- Barn 29: $6,000 L \times ((20 \times 1) + (110 \times 0.6)) \div 300 = 1,720 L$
 - where $300 = (135 + 15) \times 1 + (55 \times 1 + 15 \times 0.6) + (20 \times 1 + 110 \times 0.6)$

Figure 19. Distribution of diesel fuel consumption in LVAT farm in (%) of the total and in litres/year.

Detailed feed data as for the composition and the dose (Kg of feed type per animal) is available, as also as milk production data (in Kg) per building of interest. This data can potentially be shared privately upon request, after consulting the farm.

5.3.4 Pilot farm in Greece (poultry)

The experimental poultry pilot farm in Greece is located within the campus of the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA). It is clearly smaller than the previous 3 pilot farms as it consists of a single building with two separate rooms, occupying a total area of 90 m² (Figure 20). Room A is used for growing hens (about 450 pullets) while Room B for egg production (about 400 hens). The building's structural characteristics were recorded in detail and utilized for the simulation model as shown below.

⁹ The livestock unit, abbreviated as LSU (or sometimes as LU), is a reference unit which facilitates the aggregation of livestock from various species and age as per convention, via the use of specific coefficients established initially on the basis of the nutritional or feed requirement of each type of animal. [Source: [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Livestock_unit_\(LSU\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Livestock_unit_(LSU))]

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

(a)

(b)

Figure 20. (a) AUA poultry farm inside view and (b) location of the farm within the AUA campus.

The farm consumes no fuel for heating or cooling and solely relies to electrical energy through forced ventilation to remove the thermal loads during the warmer periods of the year. A total of **13,608 kWh** of electrical energy is demanded annually for:

- Lighting (about 3,879 kWh by: 22 1m-fluorescent lamps of 36 W each, 1 floodlight of 100 W),
- Heating (about 1,260 kWh by: 10 infrared lamps of 175 W each),
- Ventilation (about 8,360 kWh by: 2 fans of 245 W, 2 fans of 273 W and 1 centrifugal fan of 400 W),
- Manure removal (about 83 kWh by: 2 motors of 550 W),
- Feeding (about 25 kWh by: 1 motor of 550 W).

The allocation of the electrical consumption throughout a 12-month cycle is visible in [Figure 21](#).

Figure 21. Yearly allocation of the electrical energy consumption of AUA's farm per need.

Here the electrical energy demand strongly depends on the work cycle of the farm. For example, while ventilation and lighting are -almost- constant, heating only occurs when the entry of young pullets is combined to, and occurs during, the colder months (October). In the hens' room, ventilation (2 direct drive fans of 273 kW, continuously operating throughout the year) and lighting

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

(12 fluorescent lamps of 36 W, operating for 16 hours each day (night), throughout the year), do not operate during February as the room is empty of hens. Correspondingly, the pullets' room is empty during March. The energy consumed by the motors for the removal of the manure and the feeding is barely visible on the above figure. This is because their operation does not exceed the 15mins/day.

Detailed feed data composition and dose (Kg of feed type per animal type (pullet or hen)/month) has also been collected. This data can potentially be shared privately upon request, after consulting the AUA/farm.

Despite having estimated the electrical energy consumption, numerical studies were also conducted for the AUA farm/building in order to evaluate the temperature distribution and heat flow within the building for a farm/case with more data available. As previously described for the GOLINELLI farm, the thermal loads of the animals, the desired temperatures for each type of animal (in that case hens and pullets), the air (ambient) temperature and the building's details were utilized and the visualized results are presented in the following Figures (Figure 22).

(a) For ambient temperature of 7 °C (Colour scale in Kelvin)

(b) For ambient temperature of 17 °C

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

(c) For ambient temperature of 27 °C

Figure 22. Temperature distribution (colour coded scalar field) and thermal flows (vector field) in AUA farm for three different ambient temperatures.

In the above figures the colours represent the temperature gradient and the arrows the conductive heat flux. The simulations are carried out for a desired temperature of 20 °C for the hens and 30 °C for the pullets. The ambient temperature data is based on meteorological data of the past 10 years for the farm's location. Two outliers (min/max) and an average value for the ambient temperature have been depicted as shown in the captions. The variation between the temperature distribution and the thermal flows between the separate, pullets' and hens', rooms is easily observable. From the above simulations a heat transfer coefficient of 9.275 kWh/K for the specific building can be derived¹⁰.

In Figure 23 the monthly energy requirements are calculated for a full year period, as previously Figure 13 for Buildings 12 and 16 of the GOLINELLI farm. Again, the positive values represent the energy requirements (in kWh) for heating, while the negative values (in summer months) for cooling. By comparing the two graphs, it is evident that the heat transfer coefficient is of the same magnitude. This can be explained by taking into consideration the much larger surface area of Building 12, but also the superior thermal insulation.

¹⁰ How much energy should be consumed in order to raise the internal temperature by 1 degree Kelvin (K).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Figure 23. Yearly allocation of the energy requirements for temperature control in AUA farm.

5.4 Renewable Energy Potential and most promising RES in Local Farm Areas

As stated in the GA, the approach of RES4LIVE Project is based on a diversification principle and thus, different interventions are planned according to the needs and RES availability of each separate farm. The promising RES technologies that were briefly reported in Chapter 4 and will be applied in the 4 pilot farms are in short, the following:

- In the [pilot farm in Belgium](#) two types of RES will be installed according to the specific needs of the farm. (a) Two modular heat pumps of 30 kW each will provide heating and - potentially- cooling, aiming to replace the 60kW natural gas condensing boiler (estimated annual consumption of about 220,000 kWh). (b) PVT collectors will provide electrical energy and heating, by heating up the cold side of the heat pump. PVT collectors' characteristics will be defined in the context of Task 1.4.
- In the [pilot farm in Italy](#) the scope is to replace the 34 kW LPG boiler of Building 16 (nursery barn) and cover the electrical and thermal needs of this building with a thermal RES system. The system will combine a PVT system (104 kW_{th}, 20.8 kW_{el}) and a geothermal heat store (ground heat storage with vertical boreholes of coaxial types – max 10 m depth). The heat from the heat store will be moved by a heat pump, providing hot water to the building.
- In the [pilot farm in Germany](#) the aim is for the electrical and thermal energy demands for milk production to be completely covered by RES. In that context, apart from (a) the installation of a PVT system for electrical energy and heating, also (b) a biogas upgrading plant and a CNG fuelling station will be demonstrated. The electrical energy from the PV will among else be utilized to charge an electrical driven tractor. The produced biomethane will be utilized in a retrofitted for biomethane use tractor.
- In the [pilot farm in Greece](#) the aim is to eliminate the electricity consumption. Towards that goal PV panels of 8 kW_p will be installed along with inverter-driven fan (ventilation) motors. Moreover, a heat pump of 10 kW will be installed to improve the thermal comfort of the animals.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

It should be highlighted that the above RES interventions will be combined with energy efficiency measures such as insulation envelopes and equipment upgrading (LED lighting and variable-drive motors). Smart energy control will be implemented in order to cost-effectively manage the energy flows (e.g. minimise energy demand from fossil fuel consumption) while satisfying the animals' thermal comfort needs for welfare and high productivity.

5.5 Future work

As a future step, an additional Deliverable, D3.5 – *Report on measured current energy demand/consumption and distribution in the pilot farms and comparison with the estimations of D3.1 [CERTH, M24]* will be produced, as defined in the relevant Project Amendment (Reference no AMD-101000785-3).

Deliverable 3.5 will contain the energy consumption and distribution of the 4 pilot farms, ideally for a full year period, using data derived from the sensors installed in the context of Task 3.3. In case the timeframe of the scheduled installations won't allow a 12-month-long data gathering process until M24 (September, '22), the acquisition of sufficient and representative for each season data will be nevertheless pursued. This data will be compared with the estimations of the energy consumption and distribution of the current Deliverable, in order to assess the quality of the methodology of data collection as presented above ([Section 5.2](#)).

Moreover, the herein energy demand data will be utilized as initial input to the simulation tool in Task 3.4 – *Development of a farm-specific numerical platform for energy management and operations optimization (M7-30, CERTH)*, along with the necessary thermal comfort and indoor conditions of Task 3.2 and the concluded control strategies of Task 3.3, assisting in the development of specific algorithms for accurate RES production and load forecasting.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

6 CONCLUSIONS

Data regarding the energy consumption in livestock farms is currently quite fragmented. According to existent studies, the main energy consumption in typical livestock farms in EU occurs in the production of the animal feed. This stands for swine, bovine (apart from beef production) and poultry farming. On-farm energy consumption is also significant as it stands for, indicatively, about ¼ of the total energy consumption in pig, dairy and poultry farming.

On-farm energy consumption in typical livestock farms is utilized mainly for heating, ventilation, lighting, feeding, transportation and manure management, with considerable variations in the percentages of each demand in each farm type. For example, in poultry farming the leading demand is associated with heating; while in pig farming with on-farm transportation and heating. In dairy farms for milk production, also milk production processes consume a large fraction of the total energy demand.

The above general notes were in general terms also observed in the audits carried out within RES4LIVE for the 4 pilot farms; where the available data in combination with controlled estimations resulted in the depiction of the farms' annual energy consumptions/demands. The consumptions varied both in energy type and use. For example, the [swine pilot farm in Belgium](#) utilizes annually 115,000 kWh of electrical energy for multiple purposes (including a fraction for heating) and about 220,000 kWh of energy from natural gas solely for heating. The [dairy pilot farm in Germany](#) consumes annually about 201,000 kWh of electrical energy for milk production only. [Poultry pilot farm in Greece](#) despite its small size showed corresponding to the literature results as well, with ventilation fans being the highest energy consumers. The simulation for the [swine pilot farm in Italy](#) adequately depicted the temperature distribution and the energy flows with the given data; however, real energy consumption measurements will provide the most accurate picture for the two specific buildings of interest.

In all farms the trends of the consumptions' allocation throughout the year were as expected. Manure management, lighting and feeding trends were mostly stable; while heating demands and by extension the consumption of the respective energy types was higher in the colder months, while cooling demands were higher in the summer months. However, for a more accurate depiction of the current energy demands' status, the measurements that will be derived from the sensors that will be installed within Task 3.3 are expected.

Finally, based on the review onto most promising RES and energy efficiency measures, it is clear that the potential for their penetration within the livestock sector is huge not only as individual/independent technologies but also as combined solutions. These solutions will be tested within RES4LIVE, and their performance will be evaluated also in parallel with the animals' comfort. Special care should be given into the identification of the most suitable solution for each farm according to a number of factors as presented in this document. Absolute conclusions (e.g., matchings between farm types and RES technologies) can't be derived as the most suitable solutions strongly depend on these factors. Farm location, local environment, buildings' characteristics, special farm needs -such as milking needs- and policies are only some of these. In that context, the simulation tool that will be developed in Task 3.4 will evaluate the above factors considering various RES technologies, combinations, and sizing effects both for individual farms and symbiotically, for groups of farms.

If two main conclusions were to be derived from this report, these would be that (a) the relevant data available is very limited and further research is needed in order to get a better understanding of energy demand/consumption within typical livestock farms; and (b) the simulation tool of RES4LIVE

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

will strongly contribute towards the identification of RES potential in specific livestock farms, as it constitutes a demanding task that requires the combination and evaluation of essential data from various sources.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

7 REFERENCES

Akmese, S., Omeroglu, G. and Comakli, O. (2021) 'Photovoltaic thermal (PV/T) system assisted heat pump utilization for milk pasteurization', *Solar Energy*. Pergamon, 218, pp. 35–47. doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2021.02.014.

Al-Waeli, A. H. *et al.* (2017) 'Photovoltaic Thermal PV/T systems: A review', *International Journal of Computation and Applied Sciences*. International Journal of Computation and Applied Science, 2(2), pp. 62–67. doi: 10.24842/1611/0027.

Alberti, L. *et al.* (2018) 'Geothermal heat pumps for sustainable farm climatization and field irrigation', *Agricultural Water Management*. Elsevier, 195, pp. 187–200. doi: 10.1016/J.AGWAT.2017.10.009.

Basset-Mens, C. and Van Der Werf, H. M. G. (2005) 'Scenario-based environmental assessment of farming systems: the case of pig production in France', *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*. Elsevier, 105(1–2), pp. 127–144. doi: 10.1016/J.AGEE.2004.05.007.

Biomass CHP | E-RATIONAL (no date). Available at: <https://e-rational.net/applications/biomass-chp.html> (Accessed: 30 September 2021).

Bouraoui, R. *et al.* (2002) 'The relationship of temperature-humidity index with milk production of dairy cows in a Mediterranean climate', *Animal Research*. EDP Sciences, 51(6), pp. 479–491. doi: 10.1051/ANIMRES:2002036.

Canadian Wind Energy Association (2018) *Wind farms and land use*. Available at: <https://canwea.ca/blog/2018/02/21/wind-farms-land-use/> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

Caslin, B. *et al.* (2011) *Energy Use in Agriculture*.

Cederberg, C. and Stadig, M. (2003) 'System expansion and allocation in life cycle assessment of milk and beef production', *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 2002 8:6. Springer, 8(6), pp. 350–356. doi: 10.1007/BF02978508.

CERTH/CPERI (2020) *Horizon 2020 Project BioSfera Deliverable 2.3 - Analysis of selected feedstock*. Available at: <https://biosfera-project.eu/>.

Chel, A. and Kaushik, G. (2011) 'Renewable energy for sustainable agriculture', *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 2010 31:1. Springer, 31(1), pp. 91–118. doi: 10.1051/AGRO/2010029.

Choi, H. *et al.* (2012) 'Effect of heating system using a geothermal heat pump on the production performance and housing environment of broiler chickens', *Poultry science*. Poult Sci, 91(2), pp. 275–281. doi: 10.3382/PS.2011-01666.

Commission, E. (2017) *Eggs Overview*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/animals-and-animal-products/animal-products/eggs_en (Accessed: 11 August 2021).

Costantino, A. *et al.* (2016) 'Energy Use for Climate Control of Animal Houses: The State of the Art in Europe', *Energy Procedia*. Elsevier, 101, pp. 184–191. doi: 10.1016/J.EGYPRO.2016.11.024.

Cui, Y., Xue, X. and Riffat, S. (2021) 'Cost Effectiveness of Poultry Production by Sustainable and Renewable Energy Source', *Meat and Nutrition*. IntechOpen. doi: 10.5772/INTECHOPEN.97543.

Dekker, S. E. M. *et al.* (2011) 'Ecological and economic evaluation of Dutch egg production systems', *Livestock Science*. Elsevier, 139(1–2), pp. 109–121. doi: 10.1016/J.LIVSCI.2011.03.011.

Diwania, S. *et al.* (2020) 'Photovoltaic–thermal (PV/T) technology: a comprehensive review on

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

applications and its advancement', *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering*. Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH, 11(1), pp. 33–54. doi: 10.1007/S40095-019-00327-Y.

EIP-AGRI (2020) *Focus Group New feed for pigs and poultry*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/publications/eip-agri-focus-group-new-feed-final-report> (Accessed: 11 August 2021).

'Energy Savings Potential in Cyprus Subsectors: Floriculture and vegetables in greenhouses The Cyprus energy profile for the greenhouses sector: current situation and energy saving measures in combination with RES Deliverable 3.1' (2017). Available at: www.wip-munich.de (Accessed: 30 July 2021).

EUR-Lex - 32012L0027 - EN - EUR-Lex (no date). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32012L0027> (Accessed: 30 July 2021).

EUR-Lex - 32018L2002 - EN - EUR-Lex (no date). Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.L_.2018.328.01.0210.01.ENG (Accessed: 30 July 2021).

EUR-Lex - 32018R1999 - EN - EUR-Lex (no date). Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2018.328.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2018:328:TOC (Accessed: 30 July 2021).

Eurostat (2020) *Agricultural production - livestock and meat - Statistics Explained*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agricultural_production_-_livestock_and_meat&oldid=470510#Livestock_population (Accessed: 11 August 2021).

Eurostat (no date) *Milk and milk product statistics - Statistics Explained*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Milk_and_milk_product_statistics#Milk_production (Accessed: 11 August 2021).

Firfiris, V. K., Martzopoulou, A. G. and Kotsopoulos, T. A. (2019) 'Passive cooling systems in livestock buildings towards energy saving: A critical review', *Energy and Buildings*. Elsevier, 202, p. 109368. doi: 10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2019.109368.

Frorip, J. et al. (2012) 'Energy consumption in animal production - Case farm study', *Agronomy Research Biosystem Engineering*, (1), pp. 39–48. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256521473_Energy_consumption_in_animal_production_-_Case_farm_study (Accessed: 13 August 2021).

Godyń, D. et al. (2020) 'Use of Different Cooling Methods in Pig Facilities to Alleviate the Effects of Heat Stress—A Review', *Animals 2020, Vol. 10, Page 1459*. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, 10(9), p. 1459. doi: 10.3390/ANI10091459.

Gołaszewski, J. et al. (2012) *Country data on energy consumption in different agro-production sectors in the European countries - Project Deliverable 2.1*. Available at: <https://edepot.wur.nl/278550>.

Green, M. A. et al. (2002) *Solceller: från solljus till elektricitet*. Stockholm.

Guerci, M. et al. (2013) 'Parameters affecting the environmental impact of a range of dairy farming systems in Denmark, Germany and Italy', *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Elsevier, 54, pp. 133–141. doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2013.04.035.

Guide to Farming Friendly Solar (2017). Available at: https://www.uvm.edu/sites/default/files/media/solar_on_farms_report_2017.pdf (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Herbert, S. *et al.* (2014) *Renewable Energy Production on Farms*. Available at: <https://ag.umass.edu/crops-dairy-livestock-equine/fact-sheets/renewable-energy-production-on-farms> (Accessed: 12 September 2021).

Hong, S. W. *et al.* (2013) 'The design and testing of a small-scale wind turbine fitted to the ventilation fan for a livestock building', *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*. Elsevier, 99, pp. 65–76. doi: 10.1016/J.COMPAG.2013.08.020.

Horndahl, T. (2008) 'Energy Use in Farm Buildings-A study of 16 farms with different enterprises', *LANDSCAPE HORTICULTURE AGRICULTURE*.

International Energy Agency (2016) *World Energy Model – Analysis*. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-model> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

IPT Technology Ltd (no date) *GeoCube delivers reliable broiler farm heating*. Available at: <http://ipt-technology.co.uk/case-study-broiler-farm-heating/> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

Jordan, R. A. *et al.* (2016) 'Heat pump for thermal power production in dairy farm', *Engenharia Agrícola*. Associação Brasileira de Engenharia Agrícola, 36(5), pp. 779–791. doi: 10.1590/1809-4430-ENG.AGRIC.V36N5P779-791/2016.

Kalogirou, S. A. (2004) 'Solar thermal collectors and applications', *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*. Pergamon, 30(3), pp. 231–295. doi: 10.1016/J.PECS.2004.02.001.

Kharseh, M. and Nordell, B. (2011) 'Sustainable heating and cooling systems for agriculture', *International Journal of Energy Research*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 35(5), pp. 415–422. doi: 10.1002/ER.1699.

Kosmadakis, G., Manolakos, D. and Papadakis, G. (2016) 'Developments on Small-Scale Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) Systems', *Journal of Fundamentals of Renewable Energy and Applications*. OMICS Publishing Group, 6(4). doi: 10.4172/2090-4541.1000E109.

Kothari, R., Tyagi, V. V. and Pathak, A. (2010) 'Waste-to-energy: A way from renewable energy sources to sustainable development', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. Elsevier Ltd, 14(9). doi: 10.1016/J.RSER.2010.05.005.

KRISTOFERSON, L. A. and BOKALDERS, V. (1986) 'SMALL-SCALE HYDROPOWER', *Renewable Energy Technologies*. Elsevier, pp. 251–268. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-034061-6.50028-7.

Laakso, T. *et al.* (2010) 'State-of-the-art of wind energy in cold climates', *undefined*. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/State-of-the-art-of-wind-energy-in-cold-climates-Laakso-Baring-Gould/9da8e35076a4508480b48f70f59621baf6927e60> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

Lämmle, M., Herrando, M. and Ryan, G. (2020) 'Basic concepts of PVT collector technologies, applications and markets'. doi: 10.18777/IEASHC-TASK60-2020-0002.

Lee, Y. *et al.* (2010) 'Geothermal resource assessment in Korea', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. Pergamon, 14(8), pp. 2392–2400. doi: 10.1016/J.RSER.2010.05.003.

Leinonen, I. *et al.* (2012) 'Predicting the environmental impacts of chicken systems in the United Kingdom through a life cycle assessment: Egg production systems', *Poultry Science*. Elsevier, 91(1), pp. 26–40. doi: 10.3382/PS.2011-01635.

Mariita, N. O. (2002) 'The impact of large-scale renewable energy development on the poor: environmental and socio-economic impact of a geothermal power plant on a poor rural community in Kenya', *Energy Policy*. Elsevier, 30(11–12), pp. 1119–1128. doi: 10.1016/S0301-4215(02)00063-0.

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Markou, G. *et al.* (2017) *The Cyprus Energy Profile for the Animal Sector: Current Situation and Energy Saving Measures in Combination with RES*.

McAuliffe, G. A. *et al.* (2018) 'Distributions of emissions intensity for individual beef cattle reared on pasture-based production systems', *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Elsevier, 171, pp. 1672–1680. doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2017.10.113.

Morris, W. (2021) *What is biomass & is it green? A complete guide*. Available at: <https://theswitch.co.uk/energy/guides/renewables/biomass> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

National energy and climate plans | European Commission (no date). Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/energy-climate-change-environment/implementation-eu-countries/energy-and-climate-governance-and-reporting/national-energy-and-climate-plans_en (Accessed: 30 July 2021).

Nguyen, T. L. T., Hermansen, J. E. and Mogensen, L. (2010a) 'Environmental consequences of different beef production systems in the EU', *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Elsevier, 18(8), pp. 756–766. doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2009.12.023.

Nguyen, T. L. T., Hermansen, J. E. and Mogensen, L. (2010b) 'Fossil energy and GHG saving potentials of pig farming in the EU', *Energy Policy*. Elsevier, 38(5), pp. 2561–2571. doi: 10.1016/J.ENPOL.2009.12.051.

Nguyen, T. L. T., Hermansen, J. E. and Mogensen, L. (2012) 'Environmental costs of meat production: the case of typical EU pork production', *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Elsevier, 28, pp. 168–176. doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2011.08.018.

Osborn, B., Weiner, C. and Anderson, S. (2017) *Agricultural Hydropower Generation: On-Farm*. Available at: <https://extension.colostate.edu/topic-areas/natural-resources/6-708-agricultural-hydropower-generation-farm/> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

Prudêncio da Silva, V. *et al.* (2014) 'Environmental impacts of French and Brazilian broiler chicken production scenarios: An LCA approach', *Journal of Environmental Management*. Academic Press, 133, pp. 222–231. doi: 10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2013.12.011.

Röder, M. and Thornley, P. (2018) 'Waste wood as bioenergy feedstock. Climate change impacts and related emission uncertainties from waste wood based energy systems in the UK', *Waste Management*. Pergamon, 74, pp. 241–252. doi: 10.1016/J.WASMAN.2017.11.042.

Rota, A. *et al.* (2012) 'Livestock and renewable energy'. Rome: IFAD: International Fund for Agricultural Development. Available at: <https://www.ifad.org/documents/38714170/39148759/Livestock+and+renewable+energy.pdf/61af921d-a886-4558-b2d1-b97a0650ce06>.

'Saving energy on dairy farms' (2013) *Dairy Australia Limited*. Australian Government, Department of Resources, Energy and Tourism. Available at: https://www.dairyingfortomorrow.com.au/wp-content/uploads/Smarter_Energy_Use_booklet_final.pdf (Accessed: 12 September 2021).

Scurlock, J. (2014) *Agricultural Good Practice Guidance for Solar Farms*. Available at: [https://www.bre.co.uk/filelibrary/nsc/Documents Library/NSC Publications/NSC_Guid_Agricultural-good-practice-for-SFs_0914.pdf](https://www.bre.co.uk/filelibrary/nsc/Documents%20Library/NSC%20Publications/NSC_Guid_Agricultural-good-practice-for-SFs_0914.pdf) (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

Seedorf, J. *et al.* (1998) 'Temperature and moisture conditions in livestock buildings in Northern Europe', *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research (United Kingdom)*, 70(1), pp. 49–57. Available at: <https://agris.fao.org/agris-search/search.do?recordID=GB1997049166> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

	Document:	D3.1. Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D3.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/9/21

Shine, P. *et al.* (2020) 'Energy Consumption on Dairy Farms: A Review of Monitoring, Prediction Modelling, and Analyses', *Energies* 2020, Vol. 13, Page 1288. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, 13(5), p. 1288. doi: 10.3390/EN13051288.

Small, wooden windmill from Groningen incredibly popular: 'Farmers down the road want one too' - Innovation Origins (no date). Available at: <https://innovationorigins.com/en/small-wooden-windmill-from-groningen-incredibly-popular-farmers-down-the-road-want-one-too/> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

Smart Integrated Livestock Farming: integrating user-centric & ICT-based decision support platform | ICT-AGRI-FOOD Meta Knowledge Base (no date). Available at: <https://ictagrifood.eu/node/36988> (Accessed: 30 July 2021).

Song, S. H., Kang, S. Il and Hahm, N. K. (2003) 'Implementation and control of grid connected AC-DC-AC power converter for variable speed wind energy conversion system', *Conference Proceedings - IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition - APEC*, 1, pp. 154–158. doi: 10.1109/APEC.2003.1179207.

Stationary Engines | E-RATIONAL (no date). Available at: <https://e-rational.net/applications/stationary-engines.html> (Accessed: 30 September 2021).

Sustainable Livestock industry (no date). Available at: <https://www.enair.es/en/installations/installation/sustainable-livestock-industry> (Accessed: 21 September 2021).

Taylor, M. (2011) *Technology Roadmap Energy-efficient Buildings: Heating and Cooling Equipment*. Paris. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/technology-roadmap-energy-efficient-buildings-heating-and-cooling-equipment> (Accessed: 30 September 2021).

Tursi, A. (2019) 'A review on biomass: Importance, chemistry, classification, and conversion', *Biofuel Research Journal*. Green Wave Publishing of Canada, 6(2), pp. 962–979. doi: 10.18331/BRJ2019.6.2.3.

Ubbels, J. and Bouman, S. (1979) 'The saving of energy when cooling milk and heating water on farms', *International Journal of Refrigeration*. Elsevier, 2(1), pp. 11–16. doi: 10.1016/0140-7007(79)90098-7.

Upton, J. (2014) *Strategies to reduce electricity consumption on dairy farms-An economic and environmental assessment*. Wageningen University.

WEHAB Working Group (2002) 'A Framework for Action on Energy', *World Summit on Sustainable Development*.

Winkler, T. *et al.* (2016) 'From farm to fork – A life cycle assessment of fresh Austrian pork', *Journal of Cleaner Production*. Elsevier, 116, pp. 80–89. doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2016.01.005.